

Deliverable D1 : Report on an international interlaboratory comparison of new radio MIMO over-the-air system performance using project developed validated measurement methods (up to 30 GHz) for multi probe anechoic chamber (MPAC), radiated two stage (RTS) and reverberation chamber (RC) + channel emulator (CE), where applicable, for sub-6 GHz and mm wave bands taking into account ETSI TR 38.827 requirements

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AAU	Active Antenna Unit
AC	Anechoic Chamber
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
AoA	Angles of Arrival
ATF	Antenna Test Function
BLER	Block Error Rate
BSE	Base Station Emulator
BS	Base Station
BW	BandWidth
B5G	Beyond 5G
CATR	Compact Antenna Test Range
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CDL	Clustered Delay Line
CE	Channel Emulator
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CRC	Cyclic Redundancy Check
DAC	Digital-to-Analog Converter
DMRS	Demodulation Reference Signal
Dir-VAA	Directional Antenna-Based VAA
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
DUT	Device under Test
EM	Electromagnetic
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EVM	Error Vector Magnitude
FF	Far-Field
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FSPL	Free-Space Path Loss
GCM	Geometric Channel Modeling
GO	Geometric Optics
HFC	High-Frequency Convertors
HPBW	Half Power Beamwidth
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
InO	Indoor Office
IQ	In-phase and quadrature
JADE	Joint Angle Delay Estimation
LF	Low Frequency
LO	Local Oscillator
LoS	Line of Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MIMO	Multiple-input-multiple-output

Acronym	Description
mmWave	Millimeter Wave frequency band
MPAC	Multi-Probe Anechoic Chamber
NF	Near-Field
NLOS	Non-Light of Sight
NR	New Radio
OTA	Over-the-Air
PADP	Power Angle Delay Profile
PAS	Power Angular Spectrum
PBCH	Physical Broadcast Channel
PDCCH	Physical Downlink Control Channel
PDP	Power Delay Profile
PDSCH	Physical Downlink Shared Channel
PFS	Prefaded Signal Synthesis
PL	Path Loss
PSP	PAS Similarity Percentage
PWG	Plane Wave Generator
RBs	Resource Blocks (RBs)
RTS	Radiated Two Stage
RT	Ray Tracing
RC	Reverberation Chamber
RF	Radio Frequency
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
Rx	Receiver
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SSB	Synchronization Signal Block
SS-RSARP	Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Antenna Relative Phase
SS-RSRPB	Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Power per branch
Sub-THz	Sub-Terahertz band
TDL	Tapped Delay Line
TDL-B	Tapped Delay Line B
THz-TDS	THz Time-Domain Spectrometer
Tx	Transmitter
UCA	Uniform Circular Array
ULA	Uniform Linear Array
Umi	Urban Microcellular
UE	User Equipment
VAA	Virtual Antenna Array
VST	Vector Signal Transceiver
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
WP	Work Package
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
4G	4th Generation Wireless Systems
5G	5th Generation Wireless Systems
6G	6th Generation Wireless Systems

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Executive summary

This report is the sixth deliverable D1 of the MEWS project, covering the topics included in Work Package 1 (WP1) and it merges the knowledge of the consortium on practical, traceable over-the-air (OTA) metrology for 5G/6G, from FR1/FR2 into sub-THz. The overarching aim is to reduce test cost and time while maintaining accuracy, uncertainty control, and standards alignment (Third Generation Partnership Project(3GPP)/European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)). These principles guide the methods and validations presented here.

The deliverable is organized as follows: Chapter 1 is the introduction part, outlining objectives, the 3GPP/ETSI standards context, and the need for metrology that is both rigorous and deployable. Chapter 2 contains the wireless-cable multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) test solution, while in Chapter 3 a generalized OTA field-emulation framework is presented, including calibration, implementation variants, and conducted-vs-OTA throughput results. Chapter 4 describes a directional-antenna virtual array that improves SNR, allowing wider element spacing with fewer samples, and validating emulated channels with PAS/Power Delay Profile (PDP)/AOA metrics and an efficient post-processing search. Chapter 5 presents a dynamic sub-THz channel emulation, focusing on details principles, challenges and enabling techniques. Chapter 6 describes a real-world validation of the radiated two-stage (RTS) method for the link performance testing in FR2. Chapter 7 proposes reducing RMS delay spread in reverberation chambers (RC) by removing far-end clustered taps in the emulated channel. Chapter 8 studies theoretically the capacity/rank loss when CE Rayleigh fading is compounded by RC fading. Chapter 9 presents the design of the RC-plus-CE method and its testbed implementation for single-input-single-output (SISO) and MIMO configurations in both FR1 and FR2 bands, along with performance validation. Chapter 10 summarizes inter-laboratory comparisons to support traceability and reproducibility across sites, aligning measurement procedures for broader acceptance. The measurement campaigns encompass two key comparisons: (i) synthesized channel characteristics between MPAC and RC with absorber loading, and (ii) link performance testing between RTS and RC+CE. Finally, conclusions are made in Chapter 11, synthesizing findings and outlining next steps toward standardized, scalable OTA metrology for emerging wireless systems.

1. Introduction

The global shift from fourth-generation (4G) to fifth-generation (5G), and soon towards sixth-generation (6G) mobile network systems, represents more than just an increase in data rates, it signifies a transformation in how wireless networks are conceived, deployed, and used. Future systems will operate across vastly higher frequency ranges (mmWave and sub-terahertz (sub-THz)), leverage massive antenna arrays, rely on artificial intelligence and edge computing, and serve mission-critical applications requiring extreme precision in timing and reliability [1], [2]. This technological leap introduces unprecedented complexity in the design, testing, and validation of wireless systems. Measurement science or metrology is essential to navigate these challenges, offering the traceable benchmarks necessary for innovation, standardization, regulation, and industrial deployment. However, existing metrology infrastructure and methodologies are not fully equipped to handle these emerging demands.

The primary aim of the presented work in this document is to develop metrological methods that are not only scientifically rigorous, but also practical from an industrial and regulatory standpoint, i.e. minimizing cost and test time while maintaining measurement accuracy and repeatability. A key focus was placed on achieving traceability and uncertainty quantification in accordance with international standards and guidelines. The developed methods aligned with and extended relevant specifications such as [3], [4] and [5].

These metrological advancements support both multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) over-the-air (OTA) Radio Frequency (RF) conformance testing (e.g., effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) / effective isotropic sensitivity (EIS) validation, spurious emissions, and receiver sensitivity) and end-to-end system performance assessments, including throughput, beam management, and mobility handling under realistic signal conditions. Where relevant, measurement procedures were validated through inter-laboratory comparisons and collaborative test campaigns to demonstrate repeatability and reproducibility across facilities.

More specifically, the main objectives of the deliverable can be summarized as follows:

- A compact and cost-effective wireless cable test solution has been presented and analyzed. Further, a generalized wireless cable OTA testing framework for arbitrary field emulation in nonanechoic radio environment has been developed.
- Test Zone Validation for frequency range 2 (FR2) multi-probe anechoic chamber (MPAC) Using Directional Antenna Based Virtual Array
- Dynamic Sub-THz Radio Channel Emulation: Principle, Challenges, and Experimental Validation
- Real-world validation of the Radiated Two Stage (RTS) method for the link performance testing in FR2.
- Real-world validation of the two different reverberation chamber (RC) based approaches for the 5G new radio (NR) link performance testing.
- Inter-comparison between multiple link performance OTA testing methods.

2 Wireless cable testing for MIMO radios: A compact and cost-effective 5G radio performance test solution

2.1 Introduction

A device may perform poorly or not work at all without extensive testing. Therefore, testing is a required step during the stage of research, development, and production. An important step could be the validation of the 5G radio performance in realistic propagation scenarios under laboratory conditions. In the cases of 4G long-term evolution (LTE) and new radio (NR) 5G technologies in the frequency range (FR) 1 (covering the frequency range from 410 to 7125 MHz), cable tests have been used dominantly to evaluate performance. For that purpose, RF coaxial cables are used as an interface between the testing instrument ports and the device under test (DUT) antenna ports. Thus, the needed test signals can be guided without distortion to the respective antenna ports of the DUT.

Owing to the lack of an RF connector for cable testing purposes in integrated transceiver radio designs for higher frequency 5G bands at FR2 (from 24.25 to 52.6 GHz) and beyond 5G (B5G) systems, cabled measurements are no longer practical. Therefore, OTA radiated testing can be seen as necessarily solution [6]. To emulate the radio channel between the transmitter (Tx) and the receiver (Rx), radio channel emulators (CEs) have been used under laboratory conditions in both cabled setup and OTA setup solutions [7], [8], [9].

The wireless (virtual) cable solution aims to achieve identical functionality to the cable test solution, i.e. testing signals guided to the respective antenna ports with high isolation between DUT antenna ports. Recently, the wireless (virtual) cable solution for MIMO device performance testing has attracted lots of attention from the industry, academia and among the standardization bodies [10], [11], [12], [9], [13], [14]. Compensation of the transfer matrix between the OTA probes and the antenna ports of the DUT is done with the use of radio CEs in existing wireless cable solutions. However, use of the radio CEs for such a purpose would lead to waste of valuable CE resources and to expensive systems. Employing more probe antennas is a known and effective technique to improve the robustness and quality of the wireless cable connection. However, such a solution would further increase the cost of system implementation.

This subchapter based on [15] proposes a novel wireless cable implementation, which employs a stand-alone programmable amplitude and phase control network. The presented solution is simple and cost-effective. The proposed scheme is demonstrated to work in practice by performing validation measurements obtained in the vector network analyzer (VNA)-based passive measurement setup and in the active measurement setup as well. In [15], the analogy between test solutions is discussed.

2.2 Problem statement

Cabled setup and wireless cable setup are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: System diagram for the a) cabled setup and b) wireless cable setup for a $N \times M$ MIMO systems (with $M \geq N$)

Signal model derivation is presented for both setups (refer to equations (1)-(3) in [15]). $x(f, t)$, $y(f, t)$, $s(f, t)$, and $n(f, t)$ are the transmit signal vector at the base station (BS) antenna ports ($M \times 1$), the received signal vector ($N \times 1$), the desired testing signal vector ($N \times 1$), and the noise vector at the DUT antenna ports ($N \times 1$), respectively. For the cabled setup (Figure 1a), the assumption that the desired testing signal is guided to the respective DUT antenna port without any distortion can be made, i. e. $y(f, t) = s(f, t)$. \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{G} are the unknown transfer matrix between the K probe antenna ports and N DUT antenna ports, and the calibration matrix, respectively. The scheme of cable setup (Figure 1b) includes a BS emulator, a radio CE, multiple probe antennas placed in an RF-shielded enclosure, and a DUT. The number of probe antenna ports K must not be smaller than the number of the DUT antenna ports N (i.e., $K \geq N$). Therefore, in order to achieve the same functionality of the wireless cable solution as of that of the cable solution setup, the simplified problem is to design matrix \mathbf{G} such as $|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}| = \mathbf{I}$, where \mathbf{I} ($N \times M$) is the identity matrix.

CE is an important unit in the cabled setup for MIMO performance testing. As it is clear from Figure 1a, the required CE resource in the cabled setup includes M input interface and N output interface ports, and $N \times M$ digital fading channels for the communication link. As it is discussed in [12] and [9], the achieved isolation between the wireless cables determines the quality of the wireless cable connection. The quality and robustness of the wireless cable are ruled by the condition number of the transfer matrix \mathbf{A} . The latter is defined by the probe antenna, multipath propagation within the RF-shielded enclosure, and DUT antennas. Usually, the DUT is considered as a black box, because the locations and radiation patterns of DUT elements are not known. Therefore, the lack of knowledge of DUT and propagation environment makes the control the condition number of the matrix \mathbf{A} impossible. By using more

probe antennas, the condition number of \mathbf{A} can be improved. However, with the available CE implementations, such scheme will become highly costly when using a large number of probe antennas.

In the state-of-the-art implementations, the calibration matrix \mathbf{G} consists of phase and amplitude tuning networks on the CE output side (interface ports). For example, to achieve the n th wireless cable connection to the n th DUT antenna port, N phase shifters connected to the N probe antennas need to be tuned such that nulls are derived toward the other $(N - 1)$ unintended DUT antenna ports and a maximum toward to target n -th DUT antenna port, thus guiding desired testing signal $s_n(f, t)$ to the n th DUT antenna port. The n -th column vector of the calibration matrix \mathbf{G} is designed such as to establish the n th wireless cable connection.

2.3 Proposed setup

A stand-alone programmable amplitude and phase control network is presented in [15] in order to implement the calibration matrix \mathbf{G} in the wireless cable setup, thus allowing reduction significantly of the system cost and possibility to extend the method for other testing scenarios without the use of CE. A system diagram of the proposed setup is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: System diagram for the proposed wireless cable setup

A programmable amplitude and phase control network is presented to implement the calibration matrix \mathbf{G} . It is possible to generate the test signals by a generic testing instrument. Therefore, wireless cable setup without involving a CE can be achieved. With the proposed scheme, the CE resource (if required at all) can be reduced significantly and is to be equivalent to that in the cabled setup. As it is explained later on, the phase shifters in the calibration stage are tuned to estimate the transfer matrix \mathbf{A} and its inverse matrix.

K can improve significantly the condition of the transfer function matrix and thereby enhancing the wireless cable performance. A straightforward solution could be to choose large number for K . However, especially when a large K is required, the cost of a phase-amplitude control network will increase. As an alternative solution, a more cost-effective and in the same time simplified setup can be achieved by the use of an extra switch matrix, as it is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: System diagram for the proposed wireless cable setup with simplified implementation

The signal from the phase and amplitude control network is routed to the K probe antenna ports via a switch matrix with N input ports and K output ports. For that proposed scheme, to evaluate the unknown transfer matrix between the output ports of the amplitude and phase control network and the DUT antenna ports (including the switch matrix setup), the calibration procedure needs to be done before the actual throughput test. The switch matrix responses are included in the measured transfer matrix and can be calibrated out when the calibration matrix G is implemented. Therefore, calibration in advance of the switch matrix in the setup is not needed. For the proposed setup, the CE resource is independent of the number of the probe antennas K and can therefore use large number of K for improving the robustness and quality of the wireless cable in practical setup solutions.

2.4 Active throughput measurements

Figure 4: Diagram of the measurement system for proposed wireless cable setup

The diagram of the measurement system is shown in Figure 4. It consists of the commercial BS, phase and amplitude control network, power amplifiers, shielded RF enclosure, multiple probe antennas, a commercial mobile handset used as the DUT and a computer to collect the reference signal received power (RSRP) values from the DUT antenna ports via the USB cable. The power amplifiers are used for compensation of the signal loss in order to meet the requirements for the signal levels in the throughput measurements. For simplicity, the power amplifiers and the computer are not shown in the figure.

Photos of the BS and DUT in the RF-shielded anechoic enclosure are presented in Figure 5. An analog channel emulation network is used to emulate a static MIMO channel matrix with different channel ranks. It is composed of combiners, power splitters and RF cables. The channel emulation network demonstrates the impact of MIMO channel

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Photos of the measurement system: a) 5G BS and b) RF-shielded enclosure and DUT

models on the throughput results. As it will be discussed later, the analog channel emulation network is introduced after the wireless cable connection in the active throughput measurement parts is achieved. The implementation of the wireless cable is only for the downlink transmission, while the uplink transmission is conducted simply by connecting the antennas in the RF-shielded enclosure to the BS antenna ports. Detailed information for the components included in the measurement system is given in Table II in [15].

The calibration procedure is to obtain the transfer matrix A between the selected four probe antenna ports and four DUT antenna ports. In order to eliminate the instability of the measurements, an averaging over time of the RSRP measurements is performed. After the transfer matrix A is evaluated during the calibration, the inverse of A with the phase and amplitude control matrix can be estimated. The achieved isolation for all four wireless cable connections is shown in Table III in [15]. The minimum achieved isolation is 21.6 dB isolation, which confirms the effectiveness of the proposed scheme. Four wireless cable connections have been established after the calibration procedure is done. While the amplitude and phase control network, the RF enclosure, and the DUT are not changed, the wireless cable connections will be maintained during the active throughput measurement. The MIMO throughput performance testing can be conducted under an arbitrary channel conditions, once a good wireless cable connection is achieved. For simplicity, different channel models are realized with an “analog” channel emulation network after achieving the wireless cable connections. Three representative static “channel models” are implemented and presented in Figure 6.

Figure 7 represents the measured throughput for the conducted (cable) and wireless cable setups for the emulated three-channel models.

Figure 6: Diagram of the analog channel emulation network for a) H1, b) H2 and c) H3

Figure 7: Measured throughput results for the cabled and wireless cable setups for the three-channel models

As one would expect, the measured throughput increases with the increase of the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). For all cases, the measured peak throughput was achieved for RSRP -85 dBm. For channel with ranks 1, 2 and 4, the measured peak throughput is around 410, 820, and 1560 Mbps. The latter confirms the good agreement of the obtained results with its MIMO channel order. Moreover, a good agreement of measured throughput results are observed for the wireless cable and conducted cable setups for all of the considered channel models.

3. A Generalized Wireless Cable Over-the-Air Testing Framework for Arbitrary Field Emulation in Nonanechoic Radio Environment

3.1 Introduction

Radio testing for commercial products has traditionally relied on cabled connections that utilize RF connectors and passive antennas attached to the DUT. However, due to the integration of transceiver front-ends and antennas in 5G and future communication systems, conventional RF ports have become outdated. As a result, OTA radiated testing has become the standard testing method [16], [17], [18]. It is crucial to evaluate the performance of multi-antenna radios under specific propagation scenarios. For instance, a plane wave field is generally needed to assess the characteristics of the antenna radiation and the performance of RF transceivers. This plane wave field can be simulated using both direct and indirect (FF) solutions, which consist of setups like the Compact Antenna Test Range (CATR) and the Plane Wave Generator (PWG) [19]. Traditional techniques for emulating the desired plane wave field typically adhere to the concept of field synthesis. This well-established approach involves controlling the excitation of probe antennas to approximate the field within the quiet zone [20], [21]. Since these methods aim to replicate the field across the entire quiet zone, they function as black-box solutions [22]. However, this creates significant challenges regarding the positioning and number of probe antennas, the measurement range, and the overall quality of the anechoic chamber. Generally, traditional methods require the probes to be located close to the target angle of arrival (AoA), as depicted in Figure 8a.

Figure 8: Comparison between the traditional method and the proposed method

To tackle the previously mentioned issues, the authors in [23] (the work serves as a basis for the current sub-chapter) took an inspiration from the wireless cable method [12], [24], which aims to replicate the functionality of wired testing in an OTA manner without the need for actual RF cables. Therefore, a generalized wireless cable framework designed for arbitrary field emulation is proposed. The fundamental concept extends the traditional wireless cable method [19], [24] by integrating the target field vector with a calibration matrix within the phase and amplitude control network. This approach enables the direct reconstruction of arbitrary fields at the DUT ports in a cost-effective, compact, and non-anechoic environment.

Compared to the traditional field synthesis method, which requires emulating a complete target field across numerous sampling points in a quiet zone, our method simplifies the process by controlling a smaller number of complex excitations at the DUT ports. This is illustrated in Figure 8b. The proposed wireless cable framework primarily targets receiver performance testing, where the physical DUT antennas are not considered during testing; instead, they serve as interface for receiving and transmitting test signals. Once the wireless cable is set up, we can utilize various DUT array configurations (with the same number of digital ports) during testing. Finally, we experimentally emulate several exemplary signaling conditions, such as plane waves with varying AoAs, non-stationary fields, and beamforming scenarios, thereby demonstrating the validity of the proposed framework.

Owing to the highly integrated RF transceivers, the OTA testing of multi-antenna radio receivers is increasing significantly. It is of importance for these RF systems to be evaluated under given channel conditions. However, the use of conventional field synthesis techniques is not practical, because it will require rigorous anechoic environments and a large number of probe antennas for synthesis. Therefore, a generalized wireless cable framework for arbitrary field emulation is proposed in [23]. The basis idea presented in the work is to extend the traditional wireless cable technique by calibration of the transfer matrix between the probe antennas and the DUT antenna ports, and consequently loading the target field vector to emulate the equivalent field at the DUT antenna ports in an OTA manner. The framework can operate in non-anechoic environments without the need of a RF shielded enclosure. The proposed framework has been experimentally validated in a non-anechoic radio environment by verifying several unique synthesized field and performing beamforming measurements. The measured results show good agreement with the target results, demonstrating the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed framework.

3.2 Proposed generalized wireless cable framework

The proposed framework is presented in 9.

Figure 9: A diagram of the proposed generalized wireless cable framework

The received field vector at the DUT antenna ports $r_{N \times 1}$ can be written as:

$$r_{N \times 1} = A_{N \times K} \cdot G_{K \times N} \cdot p_{N \times 1} \quad (3-1)$$

$r_{N \times 1} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the received signal vector at the N DUT antenna ports. $A_{N \times K}$ is the transfer matrix from the K probe antenna ports to the N DUT antenna ports. $A_{N \times K}$ encompasses the effects of the probe antennas, the DUT antennas, and the multipath propagation channel between the probe array and the DUT antenna array. This MIMO matrix can be directly measured using an on-off procedure, during which only one probe antenna and one DUT antenna are activated at a time, while all other probes and DUT antennas remain inactive. By following this method, we can capture the chamber matrix that describes the relationship between the probe antenna ports and the DUT antenna ports. The calibration matrix $G_{K \times N} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N}$ can be obtained using the pseudo-inverse operation:

$$G_{K \times N} = (A_{N \times K})^\dagger \cdot I_{N \times N} \quad (3-2)$$

where $I_{N \times N}$ is the identity matrix. It is important to note that once the matrix G is established, the physical testing environment should remain constant. The effectiveness of the proposed framework relies on the stability of the scattering from the environment, with minimal in-band interference affecting the setup. Additionally, time-varying fading in the propagation environment can be simulated by adjusting the target field vector p , while keeping G static. The generation of the vector $p_{N \times 1}$ is determined by the characteristics of the target field. In contrast to PWG and CATR methods, which can only simulate line-of-sight (LOS) paths, the proposed framework can replicate arbitrary target fields. For more information, the reader can consider equation (2) and Fig. 3 in [23].

3.3 Measurement validation

Two measurement setups were utilized in the validation campaign, as shown in Figure 10. The x-axis is oriented along the boresight direction of the DUT antennas and is directed toward the probes. The positive x-axis points directly at the probes, while the y-axis is oriented perpendicular to the ground, with the positive y-axis extending vertically upward. The AoA θ is measured from 0° at the positive x-axis and increases in a clockwise direction. In Setup I, the reconstructed fields at the four antenna ports of the DUT were directly measured using a VNA and compared to

target values to validate the proposed concept. In Setup II, the objective is to demonstrate the DUT's beam-steering performance using the reconstructed fields. This setup incorporates four programmable phase shifters and a combiner connected to the testing antenna ports, simulating a beamformer. The phase shifters are adjusted according to the desired beam-steering angle.

Figure 10: Illustration of the measurement setup a) I and b) II with the 2-D coordinate system

The validation measurement system, illustrated in Figure 11, consists of the following components: a VNA, two uniform linear arrays (ULA), a four-way RF power splitter (used on the OTA probe side) along with four digital phase shifters and four attenuators (creating the desired field vector for the DUT ports), four digital phase shifters and a four-way RF power splitter (employed to simulate a beam-steering capable DUT). The VNA generates a continuous wave frequency signal at 3.55 GHz and the two ULA with decoupled patch antenna elements serve as OTA probes and as the DUT antenna arrays. The measurement was conducted at a range of 10.5 cm, with the spacing between ULA elements set at 0.5 wavelengths (λ) at 3.55 GHz. The two ULA were arranged facing each other during the measurements. Due to constraints related to available phase shifters and attenuators, only the four central antenna elements from both ULA were employed in the measurements. It is important to note that the 10.5 cm measurement range is significantly smaller than the far-field (FF) distance for the four-element ULA, which is 38 cm at 3.55 GHz.

Figure 11: Photo of the measurement setup in the laboratory condition

The initial phase of the measurement campaign involved recording and calibrating the four RF paths associated with the probe antennas. This step was crucial to eliminate any discrepancies among the RF chains using a programmable phase shifter and attenuator. Following this calibration, the transfer matrix A was directly measured in "on-off" mode using a VNA. It is important to note that 50Ω loads were added to properly terminate the "off" links during the "on-off" measurement, which helped to minimize potential port reflections.

For "Setup I", two measurement scenarios were conducted:

1. A plane wave was directed at a ULA with AoA at 5° , 15° , 25° , and 50° . The ULA was comprised of four isotropic antennas spaced 0.5λ apart, which was designated as the DUT. This DUT antenna configuration can be loaded.
2. Another plane wave was directed at the same ULA with AoA values of 5° and 25° . In this scenario, a faulty antenna element was incorporated into the ULA, serving as the DUT (the 3rd DUT element for the 5° condition and the 2nd DUT element for the 25° condition, respectively). It is noteworthy that the "faulty element" was simulated in the target field while all physical connections remained intact and functional.

For "Setup II", a plane wave was considered to be impinging on the ULA at an AoA of 0° . This ULA also consisted of four isotropic antennas spaced 0.5λ apart. At the DUT side, the phase shifters were adjusted to steer the beam direction from -30° to $+30^\circ$ in 10° increments, resulting in a total of seven beam-steering directions. The peak response was anticipated only when the beam-steering directions configured by the DUT aligned with the 0° direction of the plane wave generated by the arbitrary wave emulator.

Ultimately, the accuracy of the field emulation was assessed by comparing the effects observed at each of the N DUT antenna ports with the target field vector $p_{N \times 1}$ and the measured received signal vector $r'_{N \times 1}$.

3.4 Measurement results

The results of the measured complex field at the four DUT antenna ports, subjected to a plane wave with varying impinging angles, are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The measured fields at the four DUT ports for a plane wave with impinging angle a) 5° , b) 15° , c) 25° and d) 50°

There is a remarkable correlation in both amplitude and phase for all the considered angles of incidence, showing deviations between the emulated and target fields of up to ± 0.75 dB and $\pm 1.5^\circ$ for an impinging angle of 5° , ± 0.8 dB and $\pm 6^\circ$ for 15° , ± 0.7 dB and $\pm 6^\circ$ for 25° , and ± 0.25 dB and $\pm 2.5^\circ$ for 50° , respectively. The measured phase and power for the first DUT element are normalized against the target values. These results clearly illustrate that a plane wave with any given impinging angle can be accurately reproduced at the DUT antenna ports. The observed deviations may stem from uncertainties associated with the programmable shifter and attenuator, quantization errors in implementing the equivalent field vector, and non-ideal conditions in the measurement environment.

In the context of non-stationary testing, our measured results strongly align with the theoretical predictions, effectively validating our proposed scheme, as demonstrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The measured fields at the four DUT ports (with a faulty DUT element) for a plane wave with various impinging angle

The amplitude and phase deviation between the emulated and target fields for functioning elements is within ± 0.9 dB in amplitude and $\pm 0.25^\circ$ in phase for an impinging angle of 5° . For an impinging angle of 25° , the deviations are ± 0.15 dB in amplitude and $\pm 1^\circ$ in phase, respectively. In the scenario with faulty elements, an isolation of over 25 dB can be achieved to simulate the malfunctioning antenna elements for both cases (i.e., when "DUT element 3 is off" and "DUT element 2 is off"). It is important to note that isolation is practically limited by the coupling between the DUT elements. Additionally, the phase deviation is larger for the faulty element since its output power is significantly weaker, which is an expected condition. For the proposed measurement setup II, the measured DUT beam-steering pattern is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: The measured and target beamforming power pattern of the ULA under the reconstructed plane wave path with 0° impinging angle

The beamforming pattern of the DUT aligns closely with the target pattern in the reconstructed field. A noticeable peak at 0° indicates that this angle corresponds to the direction of the target plane wave. As the beam-steering angle diverges from the target path direction, there is a significant drop in power, which is as expected. The measured results confirm that the DUT performed similarly to its testing conditions under a physical plane wave field.

3.5 Conclusion

This subchapter presented a generalized wireless cable framework designed to emulate arbitrary fields at the antenna ports of the DUT. The framework was experimentally demonstrated in an open laboratory environment using plane waves with varying angles of incidence, ranging from 5° to 50° , for a DUT equipped with four antennas and a short measurement distance. The framework also successfully demonstrated non-stationary fields, achieving a difference of more than 25 dB between the “faulty” and functional DUT elements. Furthermore, a plane wave with a 0° AoA was emulated, enabling the four-element DUT to perform beam-steering operations in the presence of this emulated field. The measured results exhibited excellent agreement with the targeted results.

4. Test Zone Validation for FR2 MPAC Using Directional Antenna Based Virtual Array

4.1 Introduction

Validating and testing the performance of 5G radio devices prior to roll-outs is crucial as the commercialization process of 5G picks up in speed [25], [18]. The traditional method of conducting performance testing involves bypassing the DUT antennas and using RF cables to guide the test signals directly to the antenna ports of the DUT [26], [27]. The FR2 offers extensive spectrum sources for 5G applications [28]. However, because of the highly integrated transceiver design of the 5G NR devices, OTA testing techniques have become an unavoidable trend for performance testing [29], [30], [31] and [32]. In the available literature, the proposed OTA techniques includes wireless cable solution [33], [12], [34], reverberation chamber (RC) [35], and 3-D MPAC [20], [31], [32]. The 3GPP has chosen the 3-D MPAC method as the reference standard methodology for FR2 MIMO capable devices among a variety of OTA testing techniques. However, prior to actual measurements, the fidelity of the emulated spatial channels in a 3-D MPAC setup must be assessed and verified. Assessing the target channel models' ability to be reconstructed in the test zone is the goal of test zone validation. The traditional technique for verifying a 3-D MPAC setup's channel emulation performance relies on a virtual antenna array (VAA) made up of omnidirectional antennas. Validating the emulated channels for FR2 3-D MPAC is difficult, though, for a number of reasons. A low SNR in the measurements due to the high path loss (PL) in the FR2 frequency band could introduce errors into the estimated parameters of emulated channels. Furthermore, the large number of measurement samples needed in the test zone to accurately estimate the 3-D channel spatial profiles may necessitate a lengthy measurement period. Additionally, in order to evaluate the emulated channels using various metrics, such as PDP, AoA, or power angle delay profile (PADP), power spectra in both the angular and delay domains are needed.

This subchapter is based on the work [36]. In the latter, the authors suggest a test zone validation technique for the FR2 3-D MPAC configuration that is based on a virtual array made up of directional antennas. The suggested method requires fewer measurement samples (i.e., virtual array elements) in the test zone and can produce a higher SNR in the measurements when compared to the current method. The post-processing technique for estimating the reconstructed channel spatial profiles in the test zone is an extended sequential search algorithm. Since a directional element pattern is advantageous for suppressing both the grating and sidelobes of the virtual array beam pattern, a larger element spacing greater than half wavelength could be used to decrease the number of measurement samples.

4.2 Proposed method

As previously stated, the MPAC methodology is a common approach for testing the end-to-end performance of MIMO devices OTA [37]. In order to test 4G or 5G MIMO devices under real-world propagation conditions, multiple probes are used to reconstruct spatial fading channels defined in 3GPP 38.901 [38] with the aid of radio CE. As shown in Figure 15a, the several probes are linked to a fading CE and turned on simultaneously. In order to recreate the target channel conditions in the test zone, the different probes emit fading channel profiles that are suitably constructed. As previously mentioned, a test zone validation measurement should be used to assess how well the target channel environment has been replicated within the test zone prior to carrying out the actual testing. Data collection and signal post-processing are usually the two primary steps in the test zone validation process. The measurement setup for data acquisition is depicted in Figure 15b, where a mechanical positioner is used to move a test antenna (also known as a calibration antenna in some works) to various spatial locations to form the virtual array. The VNA records the channel frequency

Figure 15: a) 3-D MPAC setup for MIMO OTA performance testing b) Measurement system for test zone validation in 3-D MPAC

response (CFR) at each site. The post-processing process extracts the necessary evaluation metrics and the channel characteristics from the measured data. MIMO performance testing can begin after the target channel environment inside the test zone has been verified.

More precisely, the following is a summary of the comprehensive steps involved in test zone validation with the suggested approach.

- 1) In accordance with the virtual array configuration, record the CFRs for every channel snapshot at every pre-determined location.
- 2) Using the extended sequential search algorithm and the information gathered in step 1, estimate the channel characteristics (i.e., AoAs, path powers, and PDP from each probe).
- 3) Determine the channel's spatial profile by assessing metrics (such as Power Angular Spectrum (PAS) and PAS Similarity Percentage (PSP)).

The signal model for the signals received in step 1 is provided in Section II-B in [36]. The extended sequential search algorithm, which is used to determine the channel characteristics based on the CFRs that the virtual array receives, is explained in Section II-C in [36]. The reader can find the detailed explanation in the aforementioned sections. Assume that the P directional antenna elements that make up the 3-D virtual array inside the test zone radiate in a radial direction. Since directional antenna patterns can suppress the array pattern's grating lobes, the element

spacing between adjacent elements can be chosen to be greater than $\lambda/2$ [39]. In the MPAC setup, N channel snapshots stepped in the CE are used to synthesize the desired channels using Q OTA probes. The OTA probes' configuration cannot be altered because they are a part of the standardized MPAC setup design. The purpose of the current work is to verify the channel environment radiated by the OTA probes. Keep in mind that the suggested approach can, in theory, be used with any 3-D virtual array configuration.

Figure 16: Diagram of the locations of OTA probes and the 3-D virtual array for test zone validation

Figure 16 provides an example of where the virtual array and OTA probes are located. Although our work can be directly extended for dual-polarized scenarios, the antenna polarization is disregarded for simplicity's sake. Equations (1) to (5) in [36] define the CFRs received by P elements. All of the OTA probes are situated in the mid-field region of the DUT and radiate toward the test zone center because the measurement range, or the distance between the OTA probes and the DUT, is set at 0.75 m in the standard for cost-saving reasons. Since the view angle differences between any two virtual array elements and a given OTA probe are negligible, the antenna gain of any OTA probe can be roughly regarded as a constant value for virtual array elements. Figure 16 shows an example of the transmission between the fifth OTA probe and the p -th element.

In order to assess the channel environment for test zone validation in FR2 3-D MPAC, the joint angle delay power profiles of the emulated channels are necessary. MUSIC is a high-angle estimation resolution algorithm that is based on subspace. Separating the spatial covariance matrix into signal and noise subspaces and calculating the AoAs based on the orthogonality between the signal and noise subspaces is the fundamental concept. Only AoAs' information is gathered, though. Joint angle delay estimation (JADE) could also be accomplished by extending the traditional MUSIC algorithm, which is known as the JADE-MUSIC algorithm [40]. By stacking the signals that the array elements receive at all frequencies into a high-dimension vector, this algorithm takes advantage of the channel's spatial and temporal characteristics. Joint angle delay power information can be obtained by performing the eigen decomposition on the covariance matrix of that high-dimension vector. However, the direct 3-D brute-force search in the elevation angle domain, the azimuth angle domain, and the delay domain, as well as the large matrix dimension of the covariance

matrix, result in an extremely high algorithm complexity. The implemented algorithm is an extension of the N two-stage sequential search algorithm proposed in [41]. Equations (9) - (11) in [36] propose steering vector solution for estimation of AoAs. By using classical beamforming to steer the array beam to the target probe direction, the CFR and channel impulse response (CIR) at each probe direction observed by the 3-D virtual array can be determined based on the estimated AoAs and the angular location of the OTA probes. However, when the target probe and some of the other probes are in close proximity, the signals from other OTA probe directions may reduce the estimation accuracy. In order to lessen the interference from the other probe directions, nulling operations are implemented. More precisely, nulls at the other five probe directions are simultaneously formed whenever the virtual array's main beam is directed to one target probe direction.

In general, the required angular resolution and the angle range of the spatial multipath profile determine the 3-D virtual array configuration. For arbitrary 3-D spatial profiles, a sphere array that fills the entire space might be a good general option. The necessary spatial resolution determines the sphere's radius and the array's total number of elements. It is possible to optimize the 3-D virtual array configuration for a particular 3-D channel model in order to balance the number of measurement samples (i.e., the number of antenna elements in the virtual array) and the estimation accuracy. The measurement time is determined by the quantity of measurement samples. As a result, it's critical to correctly arrange the array's components so that it can offer adequate angular resolution with the fewest possible measurement samples.

Clustered Delay Line C (CDL-C) urban microcellular (UMi) and indoor office (InO) channel models are typically defined by 3GPP as reference multipath channels for performance testing in NR FR2 MIMO OTA testing. The 3-D MPAC system in this instance has six dual-polarized OTA probes positioned on a sector that is at least 0.75 meters from the test zone's center, while the test zone's radius is 0.1 meters [42]. The OTA probes are situated in the elevation and horizontal planes at angles of 5° and 25°, respectively. The 3-D virtual array can be specifically created to attain adequate spatial resolution with fewer virtual array elements for the purpose of validating the reference channels. In Section III, the precise locations of the probe antennas and virtual array elements will be provided. Because of the high directivity of the element pattern, a directional-antenna-based virtual array can have element spacing greater than 0.5. However, when the element spacing is set too large and the directive element pattern is no longer able to adequately suppress the grating lobes, it would be challenging to achieve good nulling results and accurate AoA estimation.

In theory, the virtual array can be created using a variety of directional antenna types. For practical measurements, however, directional antennas with stable phase centers and constant complex radiation patterns across the entire measurement frequencies are more advantageous. Additionally, for a path with a specific incident angle, the directional antennas with a relatively wide beamwidth will increase the 3-D virtual array's effective array elements. The same virtual array configuration will be used to increase the angular resolution with more efficient array elements. Corrugated horn antennas [39], which are frequently used as feeds for reflector antennas and anechoic chambers, are a good example of a suitable directional antenna. To attain the same angular resolution as directional antennas with wide beamwidth, the comparatively narrow beamwidth directional antennas may need a larger array aperture, i.e., a larger radius for Uniform Circular Array (UCA) and more virtual array elements. On the other hand, narrow beamwidth directional antennas typically have higher antenna gain, which can result in better SNR for mmWave measurements. An unstable phase center within the frequency bands of interest, difficulties aligning polarization and main beam direction, higher costs for directional antennas with consistent antenna gain, and continuous maintenance are some

disadvantages of using a directional antenna as the test antenna.

4.3 Simulation results

The simulation's target channel model is the conventional InO CDL-A channel model [38]. Using the measured complex antenna pattern of a corrugated antenna (model number: ASY-CWG-S-265 [39]) and the target channel model produced by the Keysight geometric channel modeling (GCM) software, the CFRs received by the virtual array elements are produced based on (1)-(5) in Section II-B in [36]. Figure 4 in [36] displays the corrugated antenna's measured complex antenna pattern at 29 GHz. It should be noted that the phase pattern is obtained by carefully calibrating the phase center location. The Half Power Beamwidth (HPBW) in the E-plane and in the H-plane of the corrugated antenna at 29 GHz is approximately 40 ° and the gain is 13.5 dBi. The objective is to use the extended sequential to estimate the channel characteristics, such as AoAs, total power, and PDP from each probe. While the gain pattern, or the amplitude of the antenna pattern, is typically found in the datasheet, the complex radiation patterns of the directional antenna may not always be available. As a result, both the steering vector estimation results in (9) and (10) in [36] are offered for discussion. The virtual array elements on the horizontal semicircle span an angle range of $[0^\circ, 180^\circ]$, while the elements on the vertical sectors span an angle range of $[-30^\circ, 30^\circ]$. The virtual array is made up of 21 components spread across a sphere with a radius of 0.06 m. There are a total of eight elements on two vertical planes and thirteen elements on the horizontal plane. For elements on the same semicircle, the adjacent element spacing is 1.5λ . The locations of the six OTA probes and the separation between them and the test zone are established in accordance with [42]. In the simulation, uses 1001 frequency points are used, covering the 28–30 GHz frequency range.

The first step is to use the near-field (NF) MUSIC algorithm to estimate the AoA of the multipath, i. e. the locations of the OTA probes. Fig. 5 [36] displays the results of the angle estimation. Compared to those where the steering vector takes the gain pattern into account, the AoA can be more clearly identified when the steering vector uses the complex antenna pattern into an account. However, by locating local maxima in Fig. 5(a) and (b) (in [36]), the AoA can be precisely estimated using both steering vectors. By guiding the virtual array beam in the direction of the desired path, the powers of the paths can be determined using the path angles that were identified in the first step. Fig. 6 in [36] shows the powers of the six probes. While the other steering vector has estimation errors of less than 0.2 dB, the powers estimated by the complex steering vector can match the target values exactly.

The array beam is then guided to the desired direction, and nulls are set to the other five undesirable signal directions, yielding the PDP. Figure 7 in [36] shows the PDPs results. The steering vector in (10) in [36] can not compensate for the phase differences between different array elements due to the directional antenna pattern, which will possibly introduce inaccuracies in the estimation results. The estimated PDPs by the steering vector in (10) [36] have small ripples with power lower than -40 dB at specific delay bins, while most parts of the plots agree good enough with the target PDPs. The obtained PDPs using the steering vector in (9) are match perfectly the target PDPs. Overall, the suggested approach us first confirmed by the simulations with the various steering vectors. While the steering vector in (10) can produce acceptable estimation results with manageable errors, the steering vector in (9) can produce excellent estimation results. In practice, a virtual array with a directional antenna with a high antenna gain and a wider HPBW in the elevation plane can estimate 3-D channels with a large elevation angle and provide better SNR than a virtual array made up of an omnidirectional antenna. Additionally, because of the large element spacing, fewer array elements are needed.

4.4 Measurement validations

As illustrated in Figure 15b, the test zone validation measurements should be carried out first to assess how well the target channels are emulated within the test zone of the MPAC setup using a test antenna and a VNA. Following channel validation, real MIMO performance testing could be carried out by placing the DUT in the test zone and substituting a BS (emulator) for the VNA, as illustrated in Figure 15a. The effectiveness of the suggested approach has been demonstrated through both an actual MIMO performance test and the test zone validation measurement. The photos of the measurement system are shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Photos of (a) OTA probe antennas and (b) DUT antenna, which is used to form the virtual array in the test zone validation measurements

Six dual-polarized OTA probes were used for the measurements, which were carried out in the 3-D MPAC. The CDL-C Urban Micro and CDL-A InO channel models, which are defined in 3GPP 38.901 [38], are the two standard channel models that the six probes used for FR2 MIMO OTA testing are primarily optimized to support. 3GPP 38.827 [42] provides a detailed location of each probe. Table II provides the target values for the OTA probe locations in our measurement coordinate system. Channel models can be mapped onto the OTA probes using the widely used prefaded signal synthesis (PFS) channel emulation technique. In order to meet the requirement of simulating the target channel models, it may be necessary to optimize the configuration of OTA probes, including their number and locations [38]. The corrugated antenna with a gain of 10-dBi and HPBW of approximately 36° at 28 GHz is used as test antenna to form the 3-D virtual array. The test antenna is moved to the specified locations within the test zone with the help of the mechanical positioner. On the x, y, and z axes, the mechanical positioner's accuracy is 0.1 mm. For further details, the reader can refer to Fig. 9 in [36], where the 3-D virtual array's configuration is presented. In total, there are 37 virtual array elements: 16 evenly distributed on two vertical sectors (element spacing: 0.61λ) and 21 evenly distributed on one horizontal semicircle (element spacing: 0.73λ). The test zone center is 0.75 meters away from the OTA probes. The

suggested method, namely test zone validation using a directional-antenna-based virtual array, can be validated even though the 3-D virtual array used in the measurement differs from that used in the simulation for the convenience of implementing a mechanical positioner.

The signals were excited by VNA and transmitted to the CE and OTA probes in turns. More specifically, the FR2 standard time-variant channel model, i.e., UMi CDL-C with 300 snapshots, was generated by Spirent CE Vertex and then radiated by six OTA probes (vertical polarized). Then, the test antenna received the signals and transmitted the signals back to VNA. The CFRs of all the measurement samples are recorded by VNA which cannot record the time-variant channels directly due to the slow frequency sweep process. Fortunately, the time-invariant channels generated in the CE can be paused and stepped in channel snapshots. The desired time-variant channel profiles can then be obtained from many separate measurements in a static environment where the VNA can be used. These data will be used to characterize the channels of the test zone in the postprocessing procedures. In our measurement, the VNA recorded single-frequency CFR at 28 GHz for every snapshot to reduce the measurement time. Since the wideband CFR data are not available, the PDP of the emulated channels cannot be obtained. Nevertheless, the main challenge of the 3-D MPAC method is to reproduce the target channel spatial profiles with a limited number of probe antennas. Therefore, the goal of our measurements is to estimate the channel spatial profiles, e.g., AoAs (the angular locations of the OTA probes in our case) and power of each probe, and calculate the evaluating metrics, such as PAS and PSP. Since the target channel models and 3-D MPAC setup are known beforehand, the proposed method can be verified by comparing the measured results with the target or theoretical values. The detailed procedures for validating the proposed method with our measurements are summarized as follows:

- 1) Set the target channel model, i.e., UMi CDL-C in the CE.
- 2) Move the test antenna to the first location and sweep all the selected channel snapshots.
- 3) Repeat 2) for all the spatial locations according to the predesigned 3-D virtual array configuration.
- 4) Estimate the AoAs and power of each probe using the extended sequential search algorithm.
- 5) The estimation results in 4) are used for a 4×4 DUT sampling array to perform classical beamforming and finally to calculate the measured PAS and PSP. The details of the calculation of PAS and PSP can be referred to [37].

4.5 Analysis of the results

Because the phase pattern of the corrugated antenna used in the measurements is not provided in the datasheet, the steering vector in (10) in [36], which only requires the amplitude of the antenna pattern is used to analyze the measured data and to obtain the results. The estimated AoA of the multipath (probe locations) and the probe index are given in Fig. 10 in [36]. The local maxima in Fig. 10 in [36] are recognized as the locations of the six probes. The target and estimated probe locations from Fig. 10 in [36] are compared in Table II in [36]. It can be observed that the estimated probe locations agree to a good extent with the target value with a maximum difference of 2° for azimuth angle and 0° for elevation angle. The directional antenna is placed away from the test zone center for constructing the virtual array. Precise positioning operations cannot be guaranteed if the phase center of the directional antenna is not accurately known, which may lead to estimation errors. With the detected angle of the paths from Table II in [36], the power of each probe can be estimated by steering the beam of the 3-D virtual array to the six detected path angles in turns. The target and measured powers for each probe are presented in Fig. 11 in [36]. Note that all the powers are

normalized to the power of the first probe. The deviations between the target powers and the measured powers for the six detected directions are respectively 0.47 dB, 0.4 dB, 0.76 dB, 0.72 dB, 0.82 dB, and 0.48 dB. The steering vector used to analyze the measured data (as it is defined in (10) in [36]) does not compensate for the phase pattern effects of the directional antenna. Therefore, the phase of the effective array elements cannot be completely aligned. It is expected that the complex steering vectors in (9) in [36] will provide a more accurate estimation of probe powers in principle as it was found in the simulation results. However, it requires a precise knowledge of the directional antenna in advance, i.e., accurate phase center location and complex antenna pattern as well as a high-resolution positioner, which may not be achieved in practice. The estimation results could significantly deteriorate if the steering vector in (9) in [36] is used with an inaccurate complex antenna pattern of the test antenna.

Finally, the measured PAS is calculated based on the detected path angles and the probe powers. The measured path angles and powers are implemented in obtaining the PAS of a standard 4 x 4 DUT array using a classical beamforming algorithm [43]. The calculated in this way PAS is equivalent to filtering the power angle spectrum of the propagation channel with the DUT array. The theoretical PAS is calculated based on the target values of probe locations and powers as a reference. The results of the theoretical and measured PAS are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: (a) Theoretical PAS and (b) measured PAS for CDL-C UMi channel model

The PSP (the reader can find more information in [37]) between the reference and the measured PAS in our measurement is 94°, which indicates the high similarity of the emulated spatial channels compared with the target channels.

A MIMO performance testing is conducted in [36]. For simplicity, we will just highlight the main important points obtained from the measurements. In the standardization, the MIMO throughput is considered as the only figure of merit for MIMO performance testing. After the emulated channel of the 3-D MPAC setup has been validated, an actual MIMO throughput performance testing is carried out. The diagram of the measurement system and the photo of the active throughput measurements are shown in Fig. 13 in [36]. The same 3-D MPAC setup with the same OTA probes configuration is used to perform the throughput measurements. An internal mobile phone mock-up is used as the user equipment (UE) and it is placed in the test zone of the 3-D MPAC. High-Frequency Convertors (HFCs) are used to perform frequency conversion between RF signals in the mmWave band and the IF band signals in the sub-6-GHz band, which is supported by the commercial CE. The same CE, i.e., Spirent Vertex, is used to generate two standard FR2 time-variant channel models, i.e., UMi CDL-C and InO CDL-A models. The BS part with two outputs used in our measurement is

composed of a commercial active antenna unit (AAU) with 1024 dual-polarized antenna elements and a dual-polarized probe antenna. At the BS, a single beam (with both the vertical and horizontal polarizations) is formed toward the dual-polarized probe antenna. The operating frequency is 26.6 GHz with 200 MHz bandwidth (BW). The two ports (for both the polarizations of the probe antenna in the BS part) were connected to the CE to form a 2 x 2 MIMO. A computer is used to control the HFCs and CE, and to collect the data. The conducted measurement was only for the downlink throughput. The results of the measured throughput for both the CDL-A and CDL-C channel models are presented in Fig. 14 in [36]. For both channels, the measured downlink throughputs increase as the RSRP increases gradually due to the improved SNR, as one would expect. The maximum throughputs are 643.3 Mb/s and 488.65 Mb/s respectively for the CDL-A and CDL-C channel models. The throughput value of the CDL-A channel model is always higher than the one of the CDL-C channel model. One possible explanation can be the different spatial channel models and the different UE velocities. The active throughput measurements show that this 3-D MPAC setup can be used for real MIMO performance testing. Therefore, this fact verifies further the effectiveness of the proposed test zone validation method.

4.6 Conclusion

Test zone validation is important for 3-D MPAC setup, because it can evaluate whether the target channel models are precisely reconstructed in the test zone. To validate the FR2 3-D MPAC setup, a 3-D virtual array based on directional antennas together with an extended post-processing algorithm is proposed in this subchapter. The simulation results using the steering vectors requiring complex antenna patterns and only the amplitude of the patterns are compared. The channel spatial profiles obtained by using the previous steering vector can closely match the target values for path angles, power of each probe and PDP. For practical implementation, the other steering vector can achieve precise estimation in path angles, resulting in less than 0.2 dB errors in power estimation, and available minimal ripples in the calculated PDP. Furthermore, the test zone validation measurement was first performed to evaluate the emulated channels in the test zone of a 3-D MPAC by using the proposed method. The measured path angles match well the target values. Comparing to the reference values, the measured probe powers have a maximal deviation of 0.82 dB. The PSP between the measured PAS and theoretical PAS is 94°. Further, an actual throughput measurement was conducted to verify the accurate evaluation of the emulated channels in the 3-D MPAC setup and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method. With many merits provided by the directional-antenna-based virtual array, it can be concluded that the proposed method will be promising solution for validation of the 3-D MPAC setup in mmWave and sub-THz frequency bands.

5. Dynamic Sub-THz Radio Channel Emulation: Principle, Challenges, and Experimental Validation

5.1 Introduction

Due to its potential to unlock enormous amounts of new frequency spectrum, Sub-THz technology has gained increasing attention from both academia and industry as one of the main contenders for the 6G systems. However, Sub-THz system designs present different challenges than those of the conventional communication systems. For short-range communication scenarios, the need for high-gain and beam-steerable antennas that are highly integrated at both ends of the communication link, the demanding propagation conditions, the scarcity of commercial RF components, and the demand for extreme data rates are the reasons behind these difficulties. Considerable work has been done to study radio channels at sub-THz, such as the development of channel sounders [44], the simulation of ray tracing (RT) [45], and standardization initiatives. Friis formula predicts that free-space path loss (FSPL) will rise. Signal transmission will primarily rely on a small number of dominant propagation paths originating from LOS and reflection transmissions. Therefore, the sub-THz channels become extremely sparse and specular. Furthermore, sub-THz channels are extremely dynamic due to their susceptibility to obstruction and environmental motion. The SNR should be kept high in order to attain the high data-rate. Unfortunately, current technology limits the Tx power and Rx sensitivity. High gain and beam-steerable antenna systems at both the Tx and Rx sides are crucial for sub-THz systems to track and align the dominant propagation paths in the channel in order to mitigate the high propagation loss and preserve the signal link quality.

Sub-THz systems of the same physical aperture can theoretically accommodate several orders of magnitude more elements than sub-6 GHz systems due to the small wavelength in sub-THz frequency bands. This allows for the provision of adequate signal power in the communication link. In real-world dynamic deployment scenarios, beam-steerable antennas are also crucial for beam management. Validating 6G radios under realistic RF propagation channel conditions is a crucial step in bringing sub-THz communication to life. Furthermore, for sub-THz radio performance testing, it would be ideal if it were possible to simulate realistic sub-THz channels in a lab setting. For testing air interfaces, a radio CE has been used extensively [46], [8], [11] and [47]. This makes it possible to conduct virtual field testing, which is necessary to test sub-THz radios in a controlled and repeatable way under a variety of representative operating scenarios. To ensure the successful rollout of sub-THz enabled 6G deployment, industry has a strong need for a standardized and affordable testing solution. To achieve sub-THz channel emulation, there are still a lot of problems to be solved. By using external frequency up-converters, the majority of commercial CEs designed for sub-6 GHz applications [46] can support mmWave frequency bands [8], [11]. Even though a single channel unit's supported system BW is rather constrained—up to 160 MHz in [8]—a BW enhancement strategy, like the band-stitching concept [11], can be used to increase the BW. In [8] and [47], for instance, CE BW of up to 500 MHz and 960 MHz, respectively, were experimentally demonstrated. Furthermore, the computationally demanding nature of implementing fading channels in a digital CE [48] means that the CE resource, i.e., the number of delay taps, is intrinsically limited. In sub-THz radios, as previously mentioned, beam-steering and beam alignment towards dominant propagation paths in a highly dynamic propagation environment are crucial and need to be assessed by suitable emulation models. Last but not least, conventional cabled testing, which necessitates a cable connection to a CE, will become obsolete due to the highly integrated and densely packed sub-THz radios with thousands of antennas.

Based on the work done in [49], the current subchapter focuses on the difficulties and enabling solutions for dynamic sub-THz radio channel emulation. More precisely, the following is a list of the major contributions:

- Covering topics like carrier frequency, system BW, CE resource, channel models, and interface between testing devices and sub-THz radios, the essential requirements for sub-THz channel emulation are identified.

- The frequency extension scheme for down- and up-converting signals from/to sub-THz bands, the band-stitching concept to improve the emulation BW, the tap resource optimization scheme to lower the required CE resource, the site-specific dynamic channel modeling taking blockage and channel transition into consideration, and the wireless cable concept for establishing an OTA connection are some of the enabling solutions that are applicable for sub-THz radios.

- Using a commercial CE platform, an experimental demonstration of fading channel replay for measured sub-THz channels is made. In the experimental setup, dynamic channels were simulated and verified using a sub-THz radio that could beam-steer and align.

5.2 Basic principle of a digital CE

A CE is specialized testing apparatus (hardware) made to simulate radio wave propagation. A simulation platform for simulating propagation channels and producing related CIRs is the channel simulator (e.g., geometry-based stochastic channel, 3GPP 38.901) or RT (usually software). In other words, channel emulation simulates real-world conditions by physically simulating radio channels in a lab setting. A standard channel simulator, RT simulation, or channel measurements are some of the methods that can be used to generate the CIRs loaded in the CE (implemented with the finite impulse response (FIR) in the baseband). For radio performance verification, the CE offers the ability to establish repeatable and controllable propagation conditions, which is frequently difficult to accomplish through field testing. Figure 19 shows an example of the digital CE.

Figure 19: Diagram of a sub-THz CE for single-input single-output (SISO) transmission, with the band stitching scheme using N sub-channels

Digital-to-analog and analog-to-digital converters (ADC) are represented by the symbols ADC and digital to analog converter (DAC) in this figure. These devices are then digitally processed, more precisely convolved, with the time-variant multipath channel profiles in real-time using digital signal processing (DSP) units. After processing, the signal is coupled into the Rx after being upconverted in the CE. Notably, probe antennas are used to transmit and receive testing signals to the CE OTA in sub-THz frequency ranges. Because they may implement flexible and standard multipath channels based on FIR filter structure, digital CEs based on tapped delay line (TDL) structure are widely used.

Keep in mind that bi-directional emulation would require twice the fading channel resources, whereas a MIMO CE with N input ports and M output ports would require $N \times M$ fading channels.

5.3 Challenges and enabling solutions for dynamic sub-THz radio channel emulation

The challenges and enabling solutions have been defined in details in [49]. They will be discussed briefly here. They are:

- Extension to sub-THz carrier frequency band: Using a mixer to up-convert and down-convert the signal frequency, existing commercial digital CEs, which were first created for sub-6GHz applications, can now cover mmWave frequency bands [8]. Frequency extension modules, which are frequently utilized in sub-THz channel sounders [44], are utilized for a wider frequency range, as illustrated in Figure 19. By appropriately adjusting the local oscillator (LO) frequency, the IF in the CE, and the multiplier in the frequency extender, the RF chain's sub-THz carrier frequency can be freely designed.
- Scheme for enhancing BW: Sub-THz BW will be used in vast quantities. The costly ADCs and DACs in current commercial CEs, which are intended for testing of current systems like 4G LTE, 5G NR have restricted system BW. In [50], a mmWave CE enabled by a software-defined radio platform achieved an instantaneous BW of 3 GHz. Recent works [11] and [47] showed how successful the band-stitching approach is.
- CE resource optimization: The delay tap resource is practically constrained for commercial digital CEs. Due to computational constraints in the DSP units, the number of delay taps per channel is decreased when additional fading channels are needed. Furthermore, the sampling frequency of commercial CEs determines the discreteness of the delays. However, the number of delay taps and positions in practical propagation channels can be arbitrary. As a result, it is essential to optimize the CE's tap resource, including the number of delay taps, their positions, and the complex coefficients that are assigned. The CE will be able to replicate the target channel characteristics as closely as feasible thanks to this improvement.
- OTA interface connection: In conventional cabled configurations, RF coaxial cables are used to route testing signals from testing instrument ports (such as CE output or input interfaces) to the DUT antenna ports, avoiding the need of integrated DUT antennas. For sub-6 GHz radios, where testing via reserved antenna connectors is practical, this technique has been the most popular. However, the usage of extremely lossy, costly, and brittle sub-THz connectors is not feasible for sub-THz radios, which are distinguished by their tiny and integrated designs. The predominant technique will therefore be OTA radiated testing, which uses sub-THz integrated antennas as direct interfaces for signal transmission and receiving.
- Models of radio channels that are appropriate for simulating sub-THz: Based on the idea of channel clusters—groups of unresolvable multi-path components—geometry-based stochastic channel modeling has gained popularity in 4G and 5G standardization. Because 4G and 5G radios have limited latency and spatial resolutions, clustering makes modeling for channels with rich multipath components easier. It might not work as well with sub-THz radios, though. There are few dominant pathways in the sparse, specular sub-THz propagation channels. Highly directional antennas are used by sub-THz radios to further filter channels spatially, producing even more sparse characteristics. Furthermore, because of their large BW and electrical apertures, sub-THz devices provide excellent latency and spatial resolution.

5.4 RT simulation

Due to slow mechanical positioning and orientation systems, recent channel measurements employing both frequency domain [44] and time-domain channel sounders [51] have concentrated on sub-THz propagation channels, usually in static situations. Dynamic spatial channel measurements are an open problem, because to the complexity and expense of real-time sub-THz channel sounders. Another method is RT simulation, which models the propagation of electromagnetic (EM) waves as they interact with materials, surfaces, and objects in complicated environments by applying the concepts of geometric optics (GO). It enables the analysis and simulation of multiple scenarios with varying configurations and environmental factors, including the location of the antenna, the characteristics of the material, and the existence of obstructions. By modifying parameter values, RT also provides flexibility for examining dynamic channel properties. For 6G [45], RT shows potential in modeling sub-THz propagation characteristics. As previously mentioned, beam-steerable and high gain antennas are essential for keeping constant alignment with the dominant propagation channel, guaranteeing good connectivity even in spite of changing transceiver placements and environmental conditions. Dynamic channels caused by the mobility of communication ends and objects must be taken into account when evaluating realistic sub-THz communication links. Moreover, real-time steering towards the most prominent propagation path requires adaptive beamforming at both communication links.

RT simulation is used to model a scenario going from non-LOS (NLOS) to LOS zones in order to illustrate dynamic channel emulation capabilities. Additionally, we used practical CEs with constrained BW and tap resources to simulate wideband dynamic channels by implementing band-stitching and CE resource optimization techniques.

Figure 20: Dynamic fading channel emulation: (a) RT simulation scenario, (b) the CIRs of the target channels over the trajectory, the CIRs of the emulated channel over the trajectory by using (c) 24 taps, (d) 12 taps, and (e) 6 taps, respectively

Two omnidirectional antennas were used as the Tx and Rx antennas in the RT simulation. They have a gain of 0 dB and a HPBW of 30° in the elevation. The height of both antennas was 1.25 meters. Figure 20a depicts the simulated scenario, in which the Rx antenna moves through 31 places in 0.5 m increments, moving from NLOS to LOS and back to NLOS zones, as indicated by the blue arrow, while the Tx antenna is at a fixed location. As seen in Figure 18a, the Rx locations are numbered 1 to 31. The 100 strongest paths from the RT simulation were chosen for each location and used as the target fading channels. The Wireless InSite 3D program was used to do the simulations. Furthermore, 3.5 GHz was selected as the RT's simulation frequency. The CE's performance is independent of the carrier frequency because all of its algorithms were implemented in the baseband. We chose the D-band at 140 GHz as the carrier frequency in the channel emulation simulation. As an example, we use four sub-bands, each spanning a BW of 135 MHz, to build a wideband CE with a BW of 500 MHz. The optimization used the measured system frequency response for each sub-channel at 135 MHz in the CE bypass mode [8]. To simulate fading channels over the intended 500 MHz BW, we use three number of taps in the CE in the simulation: 24, 12, and 6. We use the tap selection and coefficient optimization strategy technique [52] for every sub-band. Theoretically, we can establish a single virtual digital channel with a total BW of $4 \times 135 = 540$ MHz by employing 4 sub-bands, each with a frequency of 135 MHz. To assess the quality of the emulated channels, Figure 20b illustrates the CIRs of the target dynamic channels over the trajectory (i.e., 31 locations). As the Rx moves from location 1 to location 31, it is evident that the CIR progressively changes. The channel conditions changing from NLOS (at places 1–7) to LOS (at positions 8–17) and back to NLOS (at locations 18–31) is the reason of this

variation. It is obvious that for the first arrival path at each Rx location, the NLOS conditions show greater delay and lower power than the LOS conditions. Figure 20c-Figure 20e show the emulated CIRs over the trajectory with 24, 12, and 6 taps, respectively. A single color bar for Figure 20c-Figure 20e indicates that the power levels of the target channels (Figure 20b) and emulated channels (Figure 20c)-Figure 20e) have the same dynamic range. Although the emulated and target CIRs for dominant paths closely match, there are considerable differences, particularly for weaker paths when the tap count is decreased. These differences demonstrate that emulated and target channels are not the same and are caused by restrictions in commercial CEs, such as discrete delays, distortion from band stitching, system BW limitations, and a limited number of delay taps because of DSP computational limitations. To reduce insertion delay and additional latency that would arise when switching between the frequency and time domains, commercial CEs often carry out channel emulation in the time domain rather than the frequency domain. As a result, it is crucial to optimize the CE's delay taps, complex coefficients, and locations. Within the limitations imposed by commercial CEs, this optimization aims to correctly depict dominant paths while compromising in simulating weaker paths. The results of the simulation show that the tap selection and tap coefficient optimization method in [52] can successfully simulate dynamic fading channels over a targeted wide band stitched together from many sub-bands, even with a restricted number of taps. This is accomplished by using sub-band calibration in the digital channels of CEs for band stitching and fading channel emulation.

5.5 Sub-THz CE experimental measurements

Experimental measurements confirmed the concept of channel emulation in the sub-THz range. In these investigations, a commercial CE operating at sub-6 GHz was used to replicate fading channels over a wide BW. Figure 21 shows a picture of the measurement setup.

Figure 21: The photo of the measurement setup

The measurement setup consists of a commercial Keysight PropSim FS16 (used as CE), a Keysight VNA PNA-X (used as VNA) and a control PC (used to configure and control the CE for emulating specific channels). The validation of sub-THz channel emulation included into account two different kinds of dynamic channel models: “blockage scenario” and “transition scenario”. As shown in Figure 22a (LOS) and Figure 22b (NLOS with LOS obstructed by the human blocker), the “blockage scenario” uses static Tx and Rx locations and purposefully adds a “human blocker” to simulate environment changes brought on by a moving object. Assuming isotropic antennas at both ends, RT simulation is used to extend

the original measurement-based CIR in order to model this situation. As explained in [53], the RT is simulated at 140 GHz, while the channel sounding measurement spans 140-144 GHz. When human blocker moving at 1 m/s and paths approach within 0.8 meters of the human blocker’s center, a blockage event takes place. By scaling individual path gains with a time-variant attenuation factor, the human blocker’s attenuation profile, which was derived from tests at 140 GHz within a 2 GHz BW as described in [54], is incorporated into double-directional data.

Figure 22: "Blockage scenario": (a) the RT simulation scenario in the LOS case (with the blocker at position 1), (b) the RT simulation scenario in the NLOS case (with the blocker at position 2) and (c) measured and target CIRs for both cases

In order to ensure link stability, beam-steering is used at both communication ends to monitor and align with the strongest path. As a result, Figure 22a and Figure 22b, respectively, show the LOS and NLOS paths.

When one of the link ends—the Tx or the Rx—moves from the NLOS region to the LOS region while the environment stays the same, this is known as the "transition scenario" and the channel changes. In order to track the most prominent propagation path, beamforming is used at both communication ends. The primary objective is to simulate the Tx/Rx’s movement in a propagation scenario, where the LOS conditions change.

Figure 23: "Transition scenario": (a) an illustration of the RT simulation scenario and (b) the measured CIRs at 0 m, 1.04 m and 2.08 m

As shown by the blue and orange dots in Figure 23a, respectively, double directional sub-THz channel measurements covering a frequency range from 110 to 170 GHz were carried out in the corridor scenario at two Rx locations, one in the NLOS and one in the LOS location in [55]. RT simulation was used to interpolate the double directional channels for the transitional areas (shown by the gray dots) between these two locations based on measurement data. A total of seven Rx locations with a 0.35 m separation distance and a 2.08 m length were represented in the RT simulation. The RT simulation produced three channel models, with the Rx antenna positioned at the left end (0 m), center (1.04 m), and right end (2.08 m), as shown in Figure 23 as an example.

In Figure 22c, the target channel models are compared with the measured CIRs of the emulated channels in the "blockage scenario" for both "blocker" positions. "Gain" in the figure denotes the channel gain in dB, which reflects the CIR's amplitude. "Measurements" indicates the CIRs of the channel that the CE emulated and measured using a VNA, while "Model" refers to the CIRs derived from the RT simulation. We find observable differences in the channels at the two "blocker" positions. Compared to the LOS example (position 1), the NLOS scenario (position 2) has fewer paths within the 40 dB dynamic range, and the paths are less dispersed. The blocking effect and the Rx antenna's main beam direction change towards the strongest NLOS path are the two primary reasons of these variations. Multiple scattering and reflections occur when the signal deviates from a direct LOS path due to environmental factors and obstructions in NLOS situations. The CIRs of the target and emulated channels in Figure 22c were compared, and the dominating paths in both scenarios showed a satisfactory alignment between the target and emulated channels. There are some apparent delay variances for specific paths, mostly due to the discrete delays in the CE with a resolution of 5 ns. The LOS path shows a 47.1 ns delay, indicating that the Tx and the Rx are around 14.1 m apart.

For three different locations, as shown in Figure 23b, we compare the measured results with the target models in the "transition scenario". For all locations, there is a very good alignment between the target channel and the emulated channel that was measured. Some changes in the channel characteristics may be seen as the Rx antenna moves from the NLOS condition (at 0 m) to the LOS conditions (at 1.04 m and 2.08 m). In particular, when the direct LOS path takes dominance in the LOS conditions, the gain of the strongest path in the CIR rises.

Overall, the observations show that, in both the blockage and transition scenarios, the emulated channels successfully replicate the characteristics of the target channels. The measured results demonstrate how well the emu-

lated channel models can replicate wireless propagation conditions, since they closely match the expected behaviors in real-world wireless communication scenarios.

5.6 Conclusion

It is essential to assess wireless systems' performance in real-life propagation channels. The requirements, difficulties, and solutions for dynamic sub-THz channel emulation in beam-steerable sub-THz radios are discussed in this subchapter. In order to satisfy the limited CE tap resource requirements and the wideband system BW, we additionally investigate ideas like band stitching and CE tap resource optimization. We experimented with a commercial CE to simulate sub-THz channel models with a 1.4 GHz BW, concentrating on beam-steerable sub-THz radio transitions and indoor human blocking scenarios. Our experiment results showed excellent emulation accuracy.

6. Radiated Two Stage (RTS) Method

6.1 Introduction

The establishment of measurement traceability and the improvement of measurement accuracy will enable manufacturers to provide confidence in their specifications. This plays a key role in the customer/supplier relationships, for which products need to be demonstrated as 'meeting specification', regardless of who is carrying out the test or when/where the test is being performed. With the industrial exploitation and adaptation of complex 5G and beyond mobile network NR signals and multi-antenna technologies, such as, MIMO, at different radio frequency bands in emerging wireless systems, the verification of emerging NR products has become both complex and time-consuming [56]. Furthermore, as wireless communication technologies continuously evolve, performance testing through cable-based measurement methods [57] becomes increasingly difficult, not only because the antenna cannot be separated from its RF front end, but more importantly, as the number of antennas increases, especially in the case of the massive MIMO, there is an unsustainable increase in the required measurement duration. Therefore, the trend in measurement of such systems has shifted toward OTA based methods.

Efficient OTA testing measurements of 5G NR systems with many advanced features, is needed to efficiently and cost effectively assess complex new radio system performance and product conformance to specifications. International standard development bodies, such as the 3GPP [58] and ETSI [59] have been working on the OTA performance test metrics for MIMO wireless communication system, measurement methodologies, and validation procedure evaluation of 5G NR UE (e.g., 3GPP TR 38.827 [57] for MIMO 5G NR end-to-end performance). This plays an important role in ensuring the multi-antenna mobile UE meets the desired performance requirements as defined in the 3GPP protocol.

Several OTA test methods were proposed originally in the sub-6GHz 4G mobile network LTE era, which includes the MPAC [57], radiation two-stage (RTS) [60], and reverberation chamber plus channel emulation (RC+CE) [60] methods. In 3GPP TR 38.827 v16.8.0 (2022-09) [57], only the MPAC and RTS methods have been considered for 5G NR performance testing. The RTS method aims to address the core challenge of link performance measurement faced by the wireless communication system, i.e. mimicking the real-world propagation channel with its inherent special domain characteristics in a controllable measurement environment. When compared with the MPAC method, which reconstructs the multipath wireless channel in a fully anechoic chamber through an array of precisely coherent probes. The multiple duplicates of the multipath signals with different phases, amplitudes, and timing are generated by a sophisticated centralized RF signal generator instrument, distributed to and transmitted by the multiple probes typically located at the circumference of the circle surrounding the UE and combined to form the designed RF distribution at the location of the UE. The RC+CE method is a much more cost-effective solution due to its simpler measurement setup compared with MPAC and RTS methods, but has not been included in [57] due to its limited channel emulation capability.

In recent years, the suitability of various test methods has been explored at different 5G NR frequency bands, including frequency range 1 (FR1, 0.41 GHz to 7.125 GHz), frequency range 2 (FR2, 24.25 GHz to 71.0 GHz) and frequency range 3 (FR3, 7.125 GHz to 24.25 GHz) bands for evaluating the OTA performance of 5G NR MIMO system. With millimeter-wave (mm-wave) MIMO antenna technologies increasingly emerging in 5G NR mobile devices, OTA characterization under the ideal far-field condition is very costly to realize since the large-scale phased arrays and beamforming technologies are likely used in the mm-wave frequency to counter the large path loss, which requires a large size of chamber to meet the far-field condition. Currently, for a 5G mm-wave UE, only a three-dimensional MPAC solution has been selected by

3GPP [56], due to limited validation of RTS methods at mm-wave frequencies. Although mm-wave channel models can be emulated by the RTS method in principle, the RTS method has been mainly validated for 2×2 MIMO mobile handsets in sub-6 GHz. Under current 3GPP standards, the RTS method is not yet fully applicable for NR systems operating with mm-wave frequency bands due to the lack of real measurement results.

Additionally, the interest in MIMO near-field communications has grown significantly over recent years, especially towards 5G-advanced and 6G communications [61], [62], [63], [64] and [65]. Furthermore, there are higher expectations for near-field measurement than far-field measurement due to advantages, such as lower chamber realization cost, smaller footprint, and lower propagation losses [66], [67]. To verify whether the RTS method is applicable in a size-limited anechoic chamber for the mm-wave frequency band, this section presents a preliminary near-field evaluation of an RTS-based mm-wave 5G NR MIMO OTA test system newly developed at the UK National Physical Laboratory (NPL) [68]. In this section, we present our work through the following sub-sections. In Section 6.2, we will briefly introduce the general RTS principle and our approach to address the challenge in its realization at mm-wave frequencies. In Section 6.3, we provide an overview of the measurement testbed and key details in the design. The subsystem verification and the measurement results are presented, respectively, in Sections 6.4 and 6.5. Section 6.6 concludes this section.

6.2 SDR based 5G NR demodulation testbed development

For FR2, the RTS method has been extended from the conventional cable-based methods [5]. As its name implies, the RTS method consists of two stages of measurement. In the first stage, the RF signals at the receiver side are generated from a 5G NR base station emulator (BSE) and imposed a channel fading by a CE through the cable-based method. In the second stage, the RF signal of the receiver side is transmitted to the DUT through the OTA “wireless cable” method [13]. Unlike the MPAC method, the OTA step in the RTS method is only responsible for delivering the RF signals to the antenna array at the DUT in the wireless cable method. The merits of this kind of method include low complexities in testbed implementations and associated low uncertainties, as well as its less requirement for the anechoic chamber (AC) compared with the MPAC method. However, there are two key challenges to be addressed to evaluate the real-world MIMO performance of the UE. Firstly, the three-dimensional (3-D) antenna radiation pattern characteristics need to be measured and applied in the wireless channel emulator. Secondly, the crosstalk between multiple Tx probes at the testbed side and Rx antennas at the DUT side needs to be precisely measured and eliminated through the signal processing method to emulate a direct cable-based connection.

Regarding measuring the antenna radiation pattern for the antenna arrays attached to UE, one significant problem to address is the lack of accessible antenna test function (ATF) within UE available. The ATF functions allow access to the reference signal received power per branch (RSRPB) and reference signal antenna relative phase (RSARP) which are defined in 3GPP TS 38.215 [69], but are optional functions for UE. Due to the scarcity of test mobile phones with fully supported ATF software UE based on a software-defined radio (SDR) system has been developed in this project, as depicted in Figure 24. Its details will be further described in Section 6.3. A particular RSRPB and RSARP measurement function block has been developed in the software UE to measure the received downlink power corresponding to each antenna and the phase differences between the reference antenna and the rest of the antenna elements, by exploring the synchronization signal block (SSB) signal, which is the downlink broadcast signal with a typical repetition period ranging from 20 to 160 milliseconds in the time domain and 20 resource blocks (RBs) in the frequency domain.

Figure 24: Illustrative diagram for the operation of the radiated two-stage method

Note that the absolute phase in the reference antenna is not required because only the phase differences determine the spatial domain distribution for the antenna array. Additionally, with Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Power per branch (SS-RSRPB) / Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Antenna Relative Phase (SS-RSARP) measurement and a 3-D positioner, the radiation pattern of each element in the antenna array can be achieved through a serial repetition of the measurement procedure.

Regarding the second, “wireless cable” stage of RTS, in order to avoid introducing more uncertainties caused by using different instruments in capturing the OTA channel matrix, a channel estimation-based measurement and compensation method through the demodulation reference signal (DMRS) has been developed. The H-matrix, which records co-channel channel factors and mutual interferences between different Tx and Rx pairs, can be measured through the DMRS embedded in the downlink physical downlink shared channel (PDSCH) block. The inverse of the H-matrix is then calculated based on the channel estimation and applied to the link after the downlink signal passes through the channel fading model to remove the channel effects of the anechoic chamber between the Tx antennas and the UE.

6.3 Testbed setup

Figure 25 depicts the whole mm-wave RTS measurement testbed developed at NPL. The core instrument of the RTS testbed is the Anritsu BSE MT8000A. The testbed, which is equipped with up to four RF channels, can fully support up to 4-by-4 MIMO in the FR1 frequency band and 2-by-2 MIMO in the FR2 frequency band, with the addition of external mm-wave RF front ends.

The RF generation and measurement components within the RTS system are comprised of multiple sub-systems. First, a PC configured with the channel fading model generator that integrates with the digital processing module in the BSE to generate the desired MIMO channel fading model according to the relevant 3GPP standard [70]. In the RTS application, the channel fading PC has a specifically designed interface to accept the radiation patterns and inverse matrix from the first stage of the RTS measurement, with the addition of the 3GPP channel model to be added when throughput testing is required. A pair of mm-wave antennas work with the BSE to form the complete Tx side for the 5G NR downlink.

For the receiver side, a PXIe MIMO SDR testbed is formed by two vector signal transceiver (VST) PXIe-5840 from NI, together with a Keysight four-channel downconverter with the shared local oscillator (LO), and a PXIe multi-core controller. The testbed can demodulate the RF signals to up to 40 GHz and up to 1 GHz RF instantaneous bandwidth. A sophisticatedly continuous baseband processing software based on the MATLAB 5G NR toolbox was developed to fully realize the 5G NR downlink detection. A central controlling program, which includes positioner control, beam former coefficient generation/ configuration, measurement control, and performance statistic recording, was developed to coordinate the various sub-systems and complete the different measurement procedures, such as H-matrix capture, antenna radiation pattern measurement as well as the link performance testing.

Figure 25: Architecture of the Tx side of the mm-wave RTS test solution

One of the biggest challenges of the software UE's development is the real-time processing requirement from the continuous fading channel emulation. MATLAB 5G toolbox was selected for this work, which is unable to run in real-time. Having considered the unacceptable complexity increase caused by programming the NI VST field programmable gate array (FPGA) which is the traditional method to meet the real-time requirement of complex digital signal processing problems.

In this project we have realized a semi-real-time software defined radio processing system, functioning within the embedded VST Computer and using standard NI FPGA designs, allowing for the MATLAB 5G NR toolbox to be used as the low-level building blocks. Utilizing the high-throughput backbone data bus in the PXI system, the front end of the software UE software is capable of continuously capturing In-phase and quadrature (IQ) data from the multiple antennas. The architecture of the developed 5G NR software UE is shown in Figure 26. The system can support at least two receiving channels with a sampling rate of 122.88 MSPS. IQ sequences are continuously streamed from the VST to the embedded computer. Despite the real-time data streaming by the front-end, the complexity of the sequential data processing will either slow down the front-end receiver or overwhelm the system memory capacity in a relatively short time if all channels are running at the same clock frequency.

Besides the initial cell search module, which takes a long time to run but can be executed at a lower repetition rate, the software mainly includes two subsystems processing in parallel at different frequencies. The first subsystem is responsible for the time and frequency synchronization track, through an SSB-based data process including tracking

the SSB time and frequency offset, demodulating the Physical Broadcast Channel (PBCH), and performing SSB-based RSRPB/RSPRA estimation. Due to the relatively low processing frequency (typically 20 ms repetition period) and less complexity in signal processing, the part can work at the near real-time processing rate, ensuring that measured time and frequency offsets are up to date and compensated on time, accounting for clock offset within the UE and Doppler shifts, which is crucial for the performance of the receiver.

Figure 26: The architecture of the 5G NR software UE

The second subsystem which performs signal processing for the rest of the physical channels including demodulating the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) and PDSCH channels, conducting channel measurements based on the Channel State Information Reference Signal (CSI-RS), etc., is impossible to meet the real-time requirement of this part due to its complexity based on the current design solution. Instead, a continuous block of packages philosophy of design has been applied here. In this testbed design, the length of the continuous IQ data sequence which covers a sufficiently long channel period, has been screamed into the data buffer, followed by a physical layer demodulation processing at low clock frequency to deal with the complete data in the buffer in an offline mode before another data screaming is operated.

6.4 Subsystem verification

All the measurements were carried out in the NPL microwave fully anechoic chamber facility as shown in Figure 27. which has a dimension of 7 m × 6.2 m × 6.2 m. In our initial setup at the Tx end, a mm-wave hybrid beamformer was employed and connected to the BSE to generate a 5G NR Downlink signal. This includes two separately controllable RF chains for the creation of two Tx beams, emulating a 5G NR base station. At the Rx end, two wave-guide horn antennas formed an antenna array. The whole measurement was performed in the near-field range, where the distance between the Tx and Rx is 2 meters.

Figure 27: Measurement setup in NPL's fully anechoic chamber, Rx antennas on rotation platform and Tx Beamformer mounted on the right-hand side

6.4.1 Evaluation of ATF measurand stability Because the RSARP and RSRPB measurement results are sensitive to the SSB demodulation, which can be affected by the non-ideal factors of the receiver, such as timing jitter and time/frequency offset, it is important to study the stability over repetitions of the measurements. Figure 28 presents the stability evaluation of the RSARP and RSRPB at variant offset angles, which are the angles of DUT offset from the boresight of the Tx antenna array. Four different Azimuth positions of the UE were selected, which are 0, 15, 30, and 45 degrees. As the offset angle increases, the receiving power is observed to decrease, and the fluctuation is increased. From Table 1, the fluctuations of both RSARP and RSRPB under 45 degrees are acceptable. Overall, the measurement results of the RSARP are more sensitive to the lower receiving power.

Table 1: Statistics of RSRPB and RSARP Results

degree	RSRPB (dB)		RSARP (degree)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
0	0	0.005	-80.14	0.82
15	-6.11	0.015	160.9	1.11
30	-15.22	0.09	55.75	2.01
45	-18.38	0.27	67.26	4.57

6.4.2 Measured Antenna radiation pattern Figure 29 shows the radiation pattern results of the two horn antennas of the UE in the azimuth plane, determined from the RSARP measurements. Regarding the definition of the RSARP, only phase differences among the elements of DUT's antenna array are measured and the absolute phase pattern of the reference antenna is not required, which also aligns with the 3GPP spatial channel model.

6.4.3 H-matrix measurement and cancellation effectiveness Finally, H-matrix is evaluated and analyzed for its channel cancellation effectiveness. Initially, the H-matrix is measured, and its associated inverse matrix is calculated by using the channel estimation results of the PDSCH channel. In Figure 30, the frequency response of each Tx/Rx pair

is shown. An Inverse Fast Fourier transform (IFFT) is performed on these frequency responses to calculate the PDP in the time domain, and the amplitude and phase of the peak points have been recorded to form the final H-matrix. An inverse H-matrix was calculated based on the measured H-matrix and was added to the channel emulation module to cancel the crosstalk between the channels. Figure 31 presents the frequency domain channel response after the inverse matrix was imposed. A maximum 40dB cancellation gain can be achieved regarding the measurement results. The results for MIMO OTA throughout performance testing are envisaged to be presented during the conference presentation.

Figure 28: The stability study of the measurement results for: (a) RSRPB and (b) RSARP

Figure 29: Measured radiation pattern for the two antennas of the UE: (a) normalised power; (b) phase differences

Figure 30: Measured frequency-domain channel response for: (a) Tx0 to Rx0, (b) Tx0 to Rx1, (c) Tx1 to Rx0, (d) Tx1 to Rx1.

Figure 31: Frequency domain channel response after applying inverse matrix: (a) Tx0 to Rx0, (b) Tx0 to Rx1, (c) Tx1 to Rx0, (d) Tx1 to Rx1.

6.5 Link performance

This section presents the MIMO OTA performance testing results comparing different Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) for 2×2 MIMO OTA performance test at FR2 frequency band (see Figure 32) under clustered delay line (CDL) Urban Microcell (UMI) non-line-of-sight (NLOS) environment scenario for a moving user equipment (UE) with velocity of 15 km/h. Three MCS which represent low, median, and high modulation orders were chosen to assess the effect of signal-to-noise (SNR) towards the MIMO OTA link performance. An Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) noise generation module embedded within the CE was used to produce a variable-level AWGN signal alongside the desired signal, based on the target receive SNR.

Due to a bandwidth limitation caused by the RTS implementation, a maximum 20 MHz bandwidth is allocated to the PDSCH channel, corresponding to 14 RBs at a 120 kHz subcarrier spacing. The Block Error Rate (BLER) results were calculated based on decoded Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) results of 16000 transmission blocks (TBs). The throughput results were calculated based on the BLER results and theoretical peak rate under the TB configuration. The BLER exhibits relatively slow convergence across all three MCS levels, which can be attributed to the characteristics of the CDL UMI NLOS channel model.

(a)

(b)

Figure 32: Measured link performance for 2×2 MIMO OTA performance test at FR2: (a) Block Error Rate (BLER); (b) Throughput

6.6 Conclusion

The section presents a real-world evaluation of an RTS-based mm-wave 5G NR MIMO OTA test system. An SDR-based software UE emulator has been developed, which contains a fully functioning baseband processing unit compliant with the 5G NR physical layer protocol. A sophisticated system controlling program to coordinate different functional blocks in the testbed including BSE, CE, mode stirrer, and UE emulator control has been developed. Some key factors which can significantly influence the performance of the RTS such as the ATF have been carefully studied and evaluated by performing a measurement campaign in a fully anechoic chamber in the FR2 frequency band. Finally, the performance evaluation of the antenna radiation pattern and H-matrix for the RTS method in the near field is presented through these preliminary measurement results.

7. RMS delay spread reduction in reverberation chambers by channel model delay tap removal

7.1 Introduction

When performing OTA radio tests in RCs [71], the inherent delay spread in the RC can affect the signalling performance for measurements involving throughput measurements. One way to deal with this influence from the chamber is to load the RC with Radio Frequency (RF) absorbers in order to reduce the Q-factor, which is the underlying factor for the long inherent delays, normally characterized by the Root Mean Square (RMS) delay spread.

When large devices such as vehicles are tested with OTA techniques in RCs, large chambers are needed and consequently a large amount of RF absorbers to limit the RMS delay spread to limits stated by standards like [72] (3GPP).

In this section we have investigated the possibility to alter the emulated channel to get a better compliance with the stated RMS delay spread requirements for OTA measurements in RC's.

7.2 Background

7.2.1 Channel model

In this section, we used the Urban Microcell channel model (UMi), which emulates radio propagation in urban environments. It is a clustered delay line model and is defined by 3GPP in [72]. The model contains six clustered delay taps (three Rayleigh paths for each cluster), with separate amplitude profiles to simulate the multipath EM urban environment. It also contains a Doppler model to simulate moving UE.

7.2.2 RMS Delay Spread

RMS delay spread is calculated from the PDP, and definitions are found in [72]. The RMS delay spread σ_τ is computed by:

$$\sigma_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_n P(\tau_n) \tau_n^2}{\sum_n P(\tau_n)} - \left(\frac{\sum_n P(\tau_n) \tau_n}{\sum_n P(\tau_n)} \right)^2} \quad (7-1)$$

where $P(\tau)$ is the PDP, given by

$$P(\tau) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T |h(t, \tau)|^2 \quad (7-2)$$

Here $h(t, \tau)$ is the inverse Fourier transform of the of the channel matrix $H(t, f)$ which is captured by sequential VNA S21 measurements.

7.2.3 Reverberation Chambers

RCs are used for EMC and radio testing. They usually consists of a shielded cavity with conducting walls, roof, and floor with some installations to achieve alterations in the EM boundary conditions (mode stirrers), that will be moved throughout of a performed test. When stirring is performed correctly, the EM environment will be statistically isotropic and uniform [73].

Two RCs are mentioned in this report: The RC tent, which is a large RC made of conductive textile with dimensions 16x8x6 m, and a smaller fixed RC, the Fourier RC, with dimensions 3.7x2.6x4.5 m.

Ref. [72] proposes a RMS delay spread of maximum 55ns. However, this can be hard to reach in large RCs (see Figure 33) due to a huge number of RF absorbers needed. For the RC tent in this example, approximately 200 absorbers would be needed to reach this limit.

Figure 33: Delay spread vs. number of RF absorbers in the large RC tent.

7.2.4 Inherent RMS delay spread of RCs

When a channel model like the UMi is transmitted through the RC, the delay taps become "smeared out" by the Q factor of the chamber and it affects the RMS delay spread. This is called the inherent delay spread and is illustrated by the PDP measurements in Figure 34 (Fouier RC).

In Figure 35 the inherent delay spread is shown together with an emulated channel. The black line is a UMi channel measured with a conducted setup, and the blue and red lines are UMi channels, measured through the Fourier RC under different loading conditions.

Figure 34: Inherent delay spread of the Fourier RC.

Figure 35: PDP and delay spread for a UMi channel in a conducted setup, and in the Fourier RC under different loading conditions.

No.	Type	Manufacturer	Model
1	VNA	Rhode & Schwarz	ZNB-40
2	Power Splitter	Passive Device	PD-0188
3	CE	Spirent	Vertex
4	DL Antennas	RISE	Leaf
5	Measurement antenna	Rhode & Schwarz	HF-907
6	RC	RISE	Fourier (3.7x2.6x4.5 m)

Table 2: Measurement equipment.

7.3 Measurement setups

For the measurements a conducted setup was used as reference, and this can be seen in the upper part of Figure 36. The RC setup is shown in the same figure in the lower part. The instruments are shown in Table 2.

Figure 36: Conducted measurement setup above and RC measurement setup below.

7.4 Method to reduce RMS delay spread in RCs

By removing far-end cluster taps in the UMi channel, the resulting RMS delay spread through the RC is reduced, since trailing delay contributions are removed. This approach was tested for the removal of several clustered delay taps and vary the number of RF absorbers. The results can be seen in Table 3 and the Figure 37 - 38 shows some example plots.

Absorbers [-]	Taps [-]	RMS Delay Spread [ns]			
		1 GHz	2 GHz	3 GHz	4 GHz
2	3	281	286	287	292
	6	306	311	327	320
	9	311	317	331	308
	12	361	348	360	365
	15	391	384	392	397
	18	401	410	408	415
4	9	217	255	234	326
	12	277	278	285	282
	15	325	306	325	323
	18	341	344	356	358
6	9	187	202	207	205
	12	249	265	272	261
	15	300	302	300	316
	18	332	321	324	328
8	12	235	256	270	257
	15	287	298	294	293
	18	303	320	335	324

Table 3: RMS delay spread measurements with different number of delay taps, absorbers and centre frequencies.

Figure 37: RMS delay spread at 1 GHz in Fourier RC. 12 taps seems like a good choice.

Figure 38: RMS delay spread at 2 GHz in Fourier RC with 4 RF absorbers. 12 taps seems like a good choice.

7.5 Conclusion

This document investigates an additional method to tune the RMS delay spread for RC measurements involving CDL channel models. This method can reduce the number of absorbers needed to get an RMS delay spread that meets the specifications of certain testing standards. This is especially important for large RCs.

8. Theoretical study on keyhole reduction methods in reverberation chambers

8.1 Introduction

The theoretical study shown in this section is part of activity 1.1.4 in the 21NRM03 MEWS project.

The keyhole effect can appear in poor channel conditions and can reduce the rank of the communication link. This effect can also be encountered when performing communication testing in RCs with CEs when using MIMO signaling (see [74] and [75]).

This is due to that the signal is affected by more than one Rayleigh fading. In our case one Rayleigh fading is applied in the CE and another one is inherently applied in the RC. This faulty reduces the channel capacity and hence introduces an error during equipment testing.

One way of reducing this effect is to increase the number of down-link antennas in the RC. For higher order MIMO this becomes costly and impractical as a lot of antennas will be needed. As an entry to the work on efficient communication testing in the MEWS project, a method of reducing the keyhole effect and the number of RC antennas needed is theoretically investigated in this report.

8.2 Background

The MIMO channel capacity is often explained as in [76] and can be summarized as

$$C(i) = \log_2 \left(\det \left(I_{N_R} + \frac{\rho}{N_T} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H \right) \right) \quad (8-1)$$

where $C(i)$ is capacity per channel realization (e.g., RC stirrer state), I is the identity matrix, ρ is the SNR, N_T is the number of transmitters, N_R is the number of receivers and \mathbf{H} is the channel matrix.

In normal channel emulation both straight and cross Radio Links (RL) are present in the RF connection setup (see Figure 39). The proposed idea is to reduce the Rayleigh content in the channel model by removing the cross-RL and simultaneously introduce a LOS component by increasing the K-factor.

Figure 39: CE port configuration with cross-RL (left) and without (Right).

To investigate the method, a set of simulations were performed. Several channels were simulated (different \mathbf{H}) and the results for 2x2 MIMO can be seen in the plots below.

In Figure 40 the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) is plotted. Rayleigh is the theoretical reference (e.g., only a CE). *Keyhole = 2* and *Keyhole = 4* shows the signal when the CE is connected to the RC with two or four keyholes. Here the keyhole effect is present. *CE 2 straight RL* shows the CDF when the cross RL are removed. *CE Rician, 2 straight RL* shows the CDF when the cross RL are removed and a K-factor of approximately 10 dB is applied. *CE Rician, 2 straight RL* is the proposed model and aligns well with the theoretical Rayleigh signal.

Figure 40: CDF of the norm of the channel matrix (\mathbf{H}).

Figure 41: Capacity as function of SNR.

8.3 Conclusions and future work

This study shows that the keyhole effect in RC-based MIMO testing can be reduced by removing cross RL and introducing a LOS component via a higher Rician K-factor. Simulations confirm that this approach improves channel capacity without requiring additional antennas, aligning well with ideal Rayleigh conditions. Next steps include validating the method through physical measurements, testing scalability for higher-order MIMO.

9. Reverberation Chamber plus Channel Emulation (RC+CE) Method

9.1 Introduction

As the 5G and beyond communication technology is being widely commercialized, and the utilized RF band is being extended to the millimeter-waves (mm-waves), the development of MIMO OTA measurement metrology is increasingly becoming important since traditional cable-based conducted measurement methods become obsolete to the most mm-wave RF front ends due to technology development trend over their antenna and RF chain being fully integrated. As mentioned in Section 6.1, in recent years, two promising OTA methods have been proposed as candidate protocol-compliance measurement technologies for RF performance testing, namely, the MPAC and the RTS methods. The former method mimics a dynamic real-world wireless propagation environment based on multiple probes located within an anechoic chamber, aided with MIMO CE that applicable to emulate most of the test propagation channel scenarios. However, the high cost and complex implementation of the test system limit its uptake. The latter method extends the conventional cable-based conducted measurement approach to radiated OTA testing by introducing an OTA-based two-stage measurement in the anechoic chamber, with the limitation of being highly dependent on prior knowledge of the antenna radiation pattern of the DUT [60], [77], [78], [17] and [79]. CLI GUI2 RCs and the associated metrological methods are powerful tools to perform OTA based measurements for antenna [80], [68] and wireless link performance evaluations [81]. Because of their inherent multipath rich characteristics, RCs are very effective in mimicking indoor wireless propagation environments. Compared with the two types of methods mentioned above, RCs offer advantages over high measurement effectiveness and low implementation cost. However, one of the main drawbacks is their inherent long decay PDP characteristic, which limits the capability to simulate discrete delay distributed multipath statistic models, such as 5G channel model defined for the 3GPP 5G NR protocol [70], even though the RC's PDP can be modified to some extent through modifying the RC quality factor by loading it with absorbing materials [79], [81].

In recent years, researchers have proposed various approaches to overcome this difficulty. A method proposed in [82] aims to diminish the long decay PDP of RC through transforming the RC to so called time-reversal electromagnetic chamber (TREC) by incorporating a time-reversal mirror antenna array and a virtual-probe array. Although it was verified effectively to the measurement of the antenna radiation pattern, the method has yet to prove its effectiveness on emulating 3GPP standard compliant channel model. Another type of method proposed in [79], [83], [84], diminishes the long decay PDP of RC by modifying the standard CE in the baseband (BB), and synthesizes an approximate 3GPP channel model. These approaches generally have the test setup for OTA measurement, which includes a CE to simulate the protocol-compliance multipath channel fading with a baseband processing module to diminish the impact of RC's long decay PDP, and RC to build a RF propagation environment around the DUT. In [83], instead of assuming the impulse shaping in each tap, a software based modified spatial channel model extended (SCME) model [85] with certain configurable length of delay spread per tap was introduced to the CE.

The SCME model was widely used in the 4G wireless network era and has similar but smaller number of multipath discrete multitap responses to the 3GPP 5G channel model [70]. The similarity between the synthesized channel response measured by a channel sounder and the SCME channel model was evaluated in the 3GPP technical report. While being optimized by changing the length of delay spread, the unignorable residual PDP of RC in the synthesized channel response limited its performance. In [79], a modified channel simulator scheme based on introducing an extra artificial multipath pattern according to the standard channel model was proposed. Compared with the real taps of standard channel models, the artificial multipaths pose nearly equivalent delay, envelope and 180-degree phase shift.

Exploiting the high correlation between every pair of real path and artificial path, the PDP of the RC with continuous exponential decay distribution could be cancelled effectively. However, in practice, the effectiveness for the implementation of the CE can be constrained by the hardware limitation, for example, the channel sampling rate. In contrast with the open-loop solution which doesn't generate the synthesized channel model based on the measured channel response of the RC, in [84] a closed-loop solution is proposed which consists of two steps namely (i) a channel measuring step and (ii) a channel model synthesis step. However, no practical implementation or measurements were performed in this chapter.

In this section, we present a complete realization of the two-step closed-loop method and evaluate its effectiveness based on experimental measurements in the RC. This section is organized as follows: Section 9.2 presents some results on the limitations of the artificial multipath method and a description of the proposed two-step approach. Section 9.3 provides details about the measurement setup and implementation and presents measurement results and analysis. Section 9.4 provides the conclusions.

9.2 Two-Step Closed Loop Method

9.2.1 Assessment of the artificial path method According to [79], the artificial multipaths are introduced by convolving theoretical SCME taps with $\delta(t) - e^{-\partial t/\tau_{rms}} \delta(t - \partial t)$. The parameter ∂t is the delay interval between the introduced artificial paths and the true SCME taps. The parameter τ_{rms} is the RMS delay spread of the RC channel response. The effectiveness of the cancellation can be impressively high under the assumption of the introduced artificial path with a very short delay value to the true path, such as 0.1 ns. However, because of the limitation of the CE implementation, minimum available delay interval between the true path and artificial path is usually limited by the maximum available channel sampling rate and RF bandwidth of the CE. From Figure 42a, one observes that if the channel sampling rate of the CE is 100 MS/s, which results in a minimum delay interval between the real paths and the artificial paths of 10 ns, the effectiveness of the cancellation of RC's response is poor. This leads to the significant RC's channel response remaining in the synthesized channel model and can also be seen from the self-correlation factor of the RC's CIR in Figure 42b. The self-correlation factor significantly reduces as the delay interval between the artificial path and the real path increases.

Figure 42: (a) Normalized PDP of the RC after adding artificial path; (b) The self-correlation function of the RC's CIR vs delay interval

9.2.2 Two-step closed-loop method description The workflow of two-step closed loop is shown in the Figure . During the channel measurement step, an equalizer filter can be estimated based on the channel measurement results. The estimated filter can be used until the RC channel response changes due to the stirrer movement, in which case the filter needs to be updated by restarting the channel measurement. The actual RF measurement is executed in the channel model synthesis step, whereby the protocol compliant RF signal goes through a convolution module, which convolving the IQ signal by an equalizer filter achieved in the latest channel measuring step before it enters CE module. The CE introduces the multipath fading and Doppler spread according to the channel model defined in 3GPP specification. The output signal of the CE then goes to the RC, and finally to the receiver where performance statistics are performed. The target channel model (SCME model or 3GPP 5G channel) is synthesized as the following equations shown.

$$h^X(t) \otimes h^{CE}(t) \otimes h^{RC}(t) = h^{SCME}(t) \tag{9-1}$$

Figure 43: The workflow of the two-step closed loop method

The channel response of the synthesized channel model $h^{\text{SCME}}(t)$ equals the convolution of the channel response of the RC $h^{\text{RC}}(t)$ with the channel response of a CE $h^{\text{CE}}(t)$ and a derived equalizer filter $h^{\text{X}}(t)$. As $h^{\text{SCME}}(t)$ can be simulated by setting appropriate parameters of taps according to the standard channel model in the CE, i.e., $h^{\text{CE}}(t) = h^{\text{SCME}}(t)$. This means

$$h^{\text{X}}(t) \otimes h^{\text{RC}}(t) = 1, \quad (9-2)$$

where $h^{\text{X}}(t)$ is the equalizer filter of the RC's CIR. In the channel measuring step, the time-domain channel sounder captures snapshots of the RC's wireless propagation channel and estimates the accurate time-domain CIR. By utilizing a windowing technique on the estimated CIR, whose window length is based on the maximum delay of the multipath of the RC's PDP, the impact of noise on the CIR estimation can be significantly reduced. The windowed RC channel response is given by

$$h'_{\text{RC}} = \text{Windowing}(h_{\text{RC,CIR}}). \quad (9-3)$$

According to (9-2) and based on the estimated time-domain response of the RC, an equalizer filter can be derived by calculating equalizer filter coefficients with the help of domain transformation as shown in (9-4). "*" denotes the complex conjugate:

$$h^{\text{X}}(t) = \text{IFFT} \left\{ \frac{\text{FFT}(h'_{\text{RC}})^*}{|\text{FFT}(h'_{\text{RC}})|^2} \right\}. \quad (9-4)$$

9.2.3 Mm-wave and multi-channel extension Based on the SISO case, a mm-wave multi-channel extension was introduced in this section. Consider a MIMO transmission with m transmission antennas and n receiving antennas, the transmission link can be modelled by the following equation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ \vdots \\ r_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} H_{11} & \cdots & H_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ H_{n1} & \cdots & H_{nm} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ \vdots \\ s_m \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ \vdots \\ n_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (9-5)$$

Compared with the SISO case, the convolution module in multi-channel case must eliminate not only the inherent multipath channel responses of each co-channel, which is the same as SISO case, but also all path responses from cross-channels. In order to achieve this target, a per-subcarrier wised frequency-domain precoding scheme was designed. As the following precoding structure depicted, for each frequency subcarrier, a $m \times m$ precoding matrix was multiplied to the $m \times 1$ transmission vector before it was mapped to the transmission antenna array.

$$\begin{bmatrix} T_1 \\ T_2 \\ \vdots \\ T_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & \cdots & W_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ W_{m1} & \cdots & W_{mm} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ \vdots \\ s_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (9-6)$$

The precoding matrix is calculated according to the following equation:

$$H \times W = I \quad (9-7)$$

Practically, a multichannel RC channel decoupling system was designed to implement the function mentioned

above (see Figure 44). First, the four-channel VST with a multichannel RF down-converter was utilized to down-convert the multichannel mm-wave RF signals from the output of the base station emulator. After digitizing the down-converted baseband signal and transferring it by the FFT modules, frequency-domain signal vectors for all four channels are obtained in parallel. With the aid of an $m \times m$ signal distribution matrix, a MIMO precoding matrix per subcarrier can be multiplied with the frequency-domain signal vectors. After the IFFT operation, the time-domain weighted signal vectors are sent to the VST's transmitter and finally converted back to mm-wave after passing through an RF multichannel up-converter.

Figure 44: mm-wave frequency range RC channel decoupling module

In actual measurement, a multi-port PNA-X was used to work with the measurement link testbed to realize an online two-step RC plus CE method for mm-wave multi-channel scenarios. Using a high-speed RF switch, the PNA-X can be easily switched to connect to the input of the down-converter at the transmit side and the output of the receiving antenna(s) at the receiver side, for the purpose of measuring the channel responses between the input of down-converter (marked “A”) and output of the receiving antenna (marked “B”), in Figure 45. At the measurement stage, PNA-X is replaced by the Anritsu’s base-station emulator, which includes MT8000A IF module and mm-wave RF front-end modules, for the purpose of the link performance testing.

Figure 45: Two-stage testbed setup and measurement scheme using a PNA-X for mm-wave multiple channel scenarios

9.3 Subsystem verification

All the measurements presented in this section were performed within the RC of the UK NPL.

9.3.1 Channel sounding measurement To characterize the propagation channel between transmitter and receiver in the RC, a high accuracy channel sounder and the related estimation algorithm were developed. Figure 46 shows the block diagram for realization of the channel sounder system. As depicted in Figure 46, the channel sounder system was designed based on a software-defined-radio (SDR) platform. In this work, a pair of National Instrument (NI) vector signal transceivers (VSTs) PXIe-5840 are used as the RF front ends at both transmitting (Tx) and receiving (Rx) ends respectively, with up to 1 GHz RF bandwidth to provide high accurate delay estimation. Meanwhile, two FPGA based baseband processing units have been used as signal generator at Tx end and data streaming at Rx end.

Figure 46: Block diagram for the channel sounder system and setup in RC

To enable synchronization of the measurement platform, a rubidium clock unit was employed as the reference signal source which provide both Tx and Rx highly stable 10 MHz reference signal with less than 1 PS of timing error accuracy. The reference sharing scheme between the Tx and Rx combined with a hardware trigger in the controller

provides the higher synchronization and very low jitter between transmitter and receiver. At the baseband of the Tx end, a Pseudo-Noise sequence of length 4095 is firstly up-sampled to a two-fold sampling rate and passes through the root raised cosine (RRC) pulse shaping filter to achieve multipath delay resolution to less than 20 ns for the channel estimation of the RC channel. At the Rx end, a post-processing module is developed to estimate the CIR of the RC from the received streamed IQ data sequence. The post-processing module includes an 8190-points length slide correlation module, a windowing module, and a calculating module of the equalizer filter.

The time-domain slide correlation was conducted to achieve the CIR of the RC, and a square window was used to significantly reduce the impacts from the noise sample within the CIR. Finally, an equalizer filter was estimated by performing calculations with the help of domain transformation and was output to the channel model synthesis step. In addition, a cable-based calibration procedure was performed at the beginning of the measurement, allowing the effects of the Tx and Rx system response to be measured and compensated based on the calibration results in the postprocessing stage. A pair of directional linearly polarized antennas were used at both Tx and Rx ends. Table 4 lists the key system settings and parameters.

9.3.2 Setup of reverberation chamber Figure 47 shows a photograph of the measurement setup inside the RC at NPL. The dimension of the RC is 6.55 m × 5.85 m × 3.5 m, it contains one vertically installed paddle stirrer. The transmit and receive antennas are the ETS-Lindgren’s model 3117 double-ridged waveguide horn antennas, which are located at two corners of the RC three meters apart. The paddle stirrer is located between the two antennas and blocks the LoS path between them.

Table 4: Key parameters of the channel sounder

<i>Name of parameter (unit)</i>	<i>Value</i>
Centre frequency	3.5 GHz
Peak output power	30 dBm
Ref accuracy	1 ps
Symbol rate	100 MS/s
PN sequence length	4095
Pulse shaping filter	13-order RRC filter, roll-off factor 0.25
Max capture length (cycles per snapshot)	81920 (10 cycles per snapshot)
Antenna gain @3.5 GHz	6.8 dBi
Half-power beamwidth @3.5 GHz	E-plane: 68 degree; H-plane: 80 degree

Figure 47: RC measurement setups and the antenna pair

9.3.3 Setup of channel emulator The CE used in the work was based on the vector signal transceiver PXIe-5644R which is set to 100 MHz channel sampling. Two typical channel models were selected for verification: 1) the Pedestrian-B model defined in the 3GPP SCM channel model [86] which is a scenario with fewer multipaths; 2) the tapped delay line B (TDL-B) model with a 300 ns of delay spread scaling defined in the 3GPP 5G channel model [70] which is rich in multipaths. The two models are presented in Table 5 and Table 6. Limited by the SDR equipment minimum sample interval of 10 ns, several multipaths are indistinguishable and are merged in the CE. As shown in Figure 48, the TDL-B model with rich multipaths and relatively small delay intervals is set in the CE. The Rayleigh distribution can be set for each path in terms of its LoS and NLoS settings. Doppler spread can also be imposed on each path according to Jakes spectrum model determined by the velocity of the motion experienced by the DUT.

Table 5: Parameters of TAPS defined in Pedestrian-B in [86].

Tap #	delay [ns]	Power [dB]	Fading distribution	Coerced delay* [ns]
1	0.0000	0	Rayleigh	0
2	200	-0.9	Rayleigh	200
3	800	-4.9	Rayleigh	800
4	1200	-8.0	Rayleigh	1200
5	2300	-7.8	Rayleigh	2300
6	3700	-23.9	Rayleigh	3700*

*Note that due to the limitation of CE software, the last path at 3700 ns could not be set in the experiment.

Table 6: Parameters of TAPS defined in TDL-B in [70].

Tap #	Normalized delay [ns]	Power [dB]	Fading distribution	Coerced delay* [ns]
1	0	0	Rayleigh	0
2	0.03216	-2.2	Rayleigh	30
3	0.06285	-4.0	Rayleigh	60
4	0.06465	-3.2	Rayleigh	60
5	0.08610	-9.8	Rayleigh	90
6	0.08958	-1.2	Rayleigh	90
7	0.11043	-3.4	Rayleigh	110
8	0.11091	-5.2	Rayleigh	110
9	0.11256	-7.6	Rayleigh	110
10	0.15165	-3.0	Rayleigh	150
11	0.15849	-8.9	Rayleigh	160
12	0.17100	-9.0	Rayleigh	170
13	0.33063	-4.8	Rayleigh	330
14	0.38268	-5.7	Rayleigh	380
15	0.46422	-7.5	Rayleigh	460
16	0.55326	-1.9	Rayleigh	540
17	0.65057	-7.6	Rayleigh	610
18	0.84882	-12.2	Rayleigh	850
19	0.96857	-9.8	Rayleigh	910
20	1.08561	-11.4	Rayleigh	1090*
21	1.23201	-14.9	Rayleigh	1230*
22	1.28370	-9.2	Rayleigh	1280*
23	1.43502	-11.3	Rayleigh	1440*

*Note that due to the limitation of CE software, the last 4 paths could not be set in the experiment.

Figure 48: The PDP setting of CE

9.4 Measurement Results

The following subsections show, respectively, the measurement results for SISO and MIMO setups.

9.4.1 For SISO setup In Figure 49a, the PDP of RC at one stirrer position is presented which follows a typical continuous exponential delay profile with maximum delay value of approximately 2500 ns. After channel estimation and post-processing as described above, the equalizer filter was derived and output to the convolution module in the channel model synthesis step. To evaluate the effectiveness of the equalizer filter, a channel measurement which includes complete RF path in the channel model synthesis step and bypassing the CE is performed. From result of the Figure Figure 49b, it can be seen that one can achieve the promising cancellation effectiveness. In Figure 49c and Figure 49d, the effectiveness of the two-step approach for two typical standard channel model is evaluated. In Figure 49c, five discrete multipaths can be observed clearly with correct delay and power profile. Similar result could also be observed in simulation of rich multipaths scenario TDL-B of 3GPP 5G channel model from Figure 49d, where clear discrete PDP can be seen and correspond correctly to the setting in the CE.

Figure 49: (a) The PDP of RC; (b) the PDP of RC after convolving with the derived equalizer filter; (c) the PDP of the synthesized channel for model Pedestrian-B; (d) the PDP of the synthesized channel for model TDL-B with a 300 ns delay spread scaling

9.4.2 For MIMO setup Figure 50 shows the comparison of the measured PDP decoupling mode based on an inverse-matrix approach [87], by-pass mode and decoupling mode based on singular value decomposition of RC+CE for 2×2 MIMO channels. The two approaches—namely, the inverse-matrix method and the singular value decomposition (SVD) method—differ only in how they handle matrices with a high condition number. As we can see from Figure 50b and Figure 50c, a good cancellation effectiveness for the multipaths (except the first path) in every cochannel (e.g. T1R1 and T2R2) and all multipaths in all cross-channels (e.g. T1R2 and T2R1) can be observed in both methods. The inverse-matrix method showed a slightly better performance than SVD-based method. Due to fluctuation in the RF channel responses estimate caused by PDP decoupling module, obvious residuals can also be observed in the results of both methods.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 50: Measured PDP of RC+CE setup for 2 x 2 MIMO channels (a) for decoupling mode based on inverse-matrix approach; (b) measured PDP for by-pass mode and (c) measured PDP for decoupling mode based on singular value decomposition

9.5 Link Performance

This section presents the MIMO OTA performance testing results comparing different MCS for 2 x 2 MIMO OTA performance test at FR2 frequency band (see Figure 51) using RC+CE method. Three MCS which represent low, median, and high modulation orders were chosen to assess the effect of SNR towards the MIMO OTA link performance. An AWGN noise generation module embedded within the CE was used to produce a variable-level AWGN signal alongside the desired signal, based on the target receive SNR. Due to a bandwidth limitation caused by the RC+CE implementation, a maximum 10 MHz bandwidth is allocated to the PDSCH channel, corresponding to 7 RBs at a 120KHz subcarrier spacing. The BLER results were calculated based on decoded CRC results of 16000 transmission blocks (TBs). The throughput

results were calculated based on the BLER results and theoretical peak rate under the TB configuration. The BLER exhibits relatively slow convergence across all three MCS levels, which can be attributed to the characteristics of the CDL UMI NLOS channel model. The planned 4×4 MIMO OTA performance test at FR1 frequency band has not been carried out due to link establishment between the BSE and mobile UE cannot be established.

Figure 51: Measured link performance for 2×2 MIMO OTA Performance Test at FR2 using RC+CE method: (a) BLER; (b) Throughput

9.6 Conclusion

This chapter presents a novel two-step closed-loop method for accurate simulation of 3GPP 5G channel or SCME channels in an RC environment. From actual measurements in the RC, even if the channel sample rate of the CE is not very high, the efficiency of eliminating the inherent continuous channel response can be demonstrated. After evaluating the effectiveness of simulating two typical channel models in a RC environment, the method demonstrates the ability to extend the RC to performance tests defined in standards such as 3GPP, and the results can be further compared with other candidate 5G OTA methods such as MPAC and RTS. Further work to be considered includes how a reverberation chamber can emulate the specific MIMO spatial correlation.

10. Inter comparisons

10.1 Comparison of PDP from UMA channel model

10.1.1 Measurement of PDP in RC for UMA channel model

The PDP was measured in the RC Fourier at the RISE EMC testing facility in Borås, Sweden for the A1.1.5 activity in the Euramet 21NRM03 MEWS Project.

10.1.2 Measurement setup

The PDP was calculated with MATLAB from VNA S_{21} measurements (20 measurements) according to the PDP definition in 3GPP. The setup is schematically shown in Figure 52. The UMA channel model was implemented in a CE with a modulation bandwidth of 40 MHz. The signalling was configured for a 2x2 MIMO use case and the measurements were performed at a center frequency of 3 GHz. To decrease the delay spread influence of the RC, eight RF absorbers were placed at random positions in the RC. The UE speed was set to 30 km/h in the CE.

Figure 52: PDP measurement setup.

No.	Type	Manufacturer	Model
1	VNA	Rhode & Schwarz	ZNB-40
2	Power Splitter	Passive Device	PD-0188
3	CE	Spirent	Vertex
4	DL Antennas	RISE	Leaf
5	Measurement antenna	Rhode & Schwarz	HF-907
6	RC	RISE	Fourier (3.7x2.6x4.5 m)

Table 7: Measurement equipment.

10.1.3 Results

In Figure 53 the measured PDP can be seen together with the nominal path delays from the UMA channel model.

Figure 53: Measured PDP in RC with a UMA channel model at center frequency 3 GHz with 8 absorbers

10.2 Intercomparison between RTS and RC+CE methods

This subchapter presents the inter-laboratory comparison for the OTA performance testing of the device under test DUT, the software-defined radio (SDR) system using RTS and RC+CE methods.

10.2.1 Introduction Antenna measurement facility intercomparison activities have become mandatory to achieve or maintain official accreditation such as ISO 17025 [64]. The main goal of such activities is to provide opportunities for the participants to validate and document their laboratory proficiency and competence by comparison with other facilities. They constitute a crucial foundation for validation of measurement accuracy among participants and provide an important prerequisite for certification of facilities as well as inputs to standards and research on measurement uncertainties [88]. The following sections present the details of the intercomparison carried out between the RTS and RC+CE methods at the UK National Physical Laboratory for the same DUT.

10.2.2 Measurement Setup This section shows the relevant measurement setups and equipment settings for the inter-laboratory comparison.

10.2.2.1 Equipment settings This subsection presents the equipment settings for BSE and channel emulator (CE) for different DUT, namely, the mobile UE and the SDR system.

1. Base Station Emulator (BSE) Configuration

Table 8 shows the BSE configurations for the 5G NR compliant SDR receiver system.

Table 8: BSE configuration for 5G NR compliant SDR system

Parameter	Value
Frequency range	FR2, band 258, centre frequency 25.875 GHz
Transmission link	MIMO 2×2 downlink
TDD	5 slots cycle, 3 of 5 for downlink
Subcarrier space	120 kHz
Bandwidth	RTS: 20 MHz, 14 RB at 120 kHz SC RC: 10 MHz, 7 RB at 120 kHz SC (limited by the RC+CE testbed implementation)
Measurement mode	Non-call mode

2. Channel Emulator Configuration

A CDL channel model was generated by using Anritsu's channel emulator module according to 3GPP SCME UMA channel model defined in 3GPP TR 37.976 [89]. Three types of antenna arrays were defined, including SISO, 2×2 MIMO, and 4×4 MIMO. UE moving velocity was set to 30kmh. Figure 54 shows the channel emulator configuration for the 5G NR compliant SDR system.

Figure 54: Channel Emulator configuration for 5G NR SDR system

10.2.2.2 RTS measurement setup for the Inter-comparison Figure 55 to Figure 58 show the RTS measurement setup in NPL fully anechoic chamber for the inter-comparison, the antenna under test radiation pattern, and the measured H-matrix before and after the implementation of inverse H-matrix cancellation, respectively.

Figure 55: Measurement setup for RTS method

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 56: The antenna (MVG QR18000) under test radiation pattern: (a) Azimuth cut; (b) Elevation cut; (c) 3-D plot

Figure 57: Measured H-matrix before implementation of inverse H-matrix cancellation: (a) h_{11} ; (b) h_{12} ; (c) h_{21} ; (d) h_{22}

Figure 58: Measured H-matrix after implementation of inverse H-matrix cancellation: (a) h11; (b) h12; (c) h21; (d) h22

10.2.3 Intercomparison results Figure 59 shows the RTS and RC+CE inter-laboratory comparison results comparing different MCS for 2×2 MIMO OTA performance test at FR2 frequency band under CDL UMI NLOS environment scenario for a moving UE with a velocity of 15 kmh. As depicted in Figure 59, a general good match between RTS and RC+CE methods can be observed in both BLER and throughput measurement results. Such achieved agreement is envisaged because of a low correlation between two receiving antennas with mutual orthogonal polarizations, which leads to a lower sensitivity to the differences from the spatial domain between the two methods. Due to a maximum bandwidth difference, the throughput results of RC plus CE have been doubled for the sake of the same allocation RB resources.

(a)

(b)

Figure 59: RC+CE measurement setup for the inter-comparison: (a) BLER; (b) Throughput

10.2.4 Conclusion In this chapter, an inter-laboratory comparison between RTS and RC+CE methods for the MIMO OTA link performance testing of the mm-wave 2×2 MIMO DUT has been carried out. A SDR-based 5G NR receiver system with an MVG quad-ridged horn antenna was used as DUT in both the measurements. The measurement results indicate a generally good agreement between the two methods, demonstrating their effectiveness for the selected measurement scenarios.

11. Conclusion

This deliverable gathered, advanced, and validated a set of metrology methods that make OTA testing practical, traceable, and scalable as industry moves from 5G toward sub-THz 6G. The overarching goal has been to reduce cost and test time while preserving accuracy and repeatability—firmly grounded in standards—and to ensure that laboratory evaluations are representative of real-world performance. These aims guided all activities and were framed explicitly in the introduction, including the emphasis on uncertainty, traceability, and alignment with established 3GPP/ETSI specifications.

A first contribution is a compact, cost-effective “wireless cable” solution for MIMO radio testing. By establishing stable port-to-port OTA links inside a small RF enclosure and calibrating the probe–DUT transfer matrix, we reproduced cabled functionality without consuming scarce channel-emulator resources. The approach delivered strong isolation across multiple links and—critically—produced throughput results that track conducted measurements across several MIMO channel ranks. Peak rates on representative rank-1, rank-2, and rank-4 cases closely matched their conducted counterparts at comparable RSRP levels, supporting wireless cable as a viable, industry-ready path for 5G FR1/FR2 device performance testing.

Building on this principle, we generalized the wireless-cable concept into a framework for arbitrary field emulation in non-anechoic environments. Rather than synthesizing a full quiet-zone field as in classic array-based methods, the proposed approach measures the chamber matrix A between K probes and N DUT ports and then loads a “target field” at the DUT via a calibration matrix $G = A^\dagger I_N$, effectively reconstructing the desired receive vector directly at the DUT ports. This reduces hardware complexity, relaxes anechoic requirements, and enables emulation of plane waves with varying AoA, non-stationary fields, and beamforming scenarios. Laboratory demonstrations verified robustness in a standard room environment, linking metrology-grade reproducibility with pragmatic test setups.

To ensure that MPAC setups faithfully realize 3GPP spatial channels at FR2, we developed and validated a Dir-VAA for test-zone validation. Relative to traditional omnidirectional virtual arrays, the Dir-VAA improves SNR, reduces required samples through larger inter-element spacing (thanks to sidelobe suppression), and shortens measurement time. Measurements showed high agreement between emulated and target channels: probe-power deviations remained well within a tight tolerance window, the PAS similarity was high, and downlink throughput behavior remained consistent under canonical CDL profiles. These findings confirm suitability for real MIMO performance testing while keeping measurement budgets under control.

Looking ahead to 6G, we investigated *dynamic sub-THz channel emulation*. We outlined an end-to-end chain for digital channel emulation at sub-THz, including frequency extension, band-stitching for wide BWs, and tap-resource optimization to stay within practical DSP limits—while still capturing dominant paths under blockage and transition dynamics. Using a commercial platform, we emulated dynamic sub-THz channels with multi-gigahertz effective BWs and validated the approach with beam-steerable radios and human-blockage scenarios, demonstrating accurate reproduction of target CIRs and path dynamics within emulator constraints.

Two reverberation-chamber (RC) studies addressed pressing OTA challenges. First, *RMS delay-spread reduction* was tackled by shaping the *emulated* channel: removing far-end clustered delay taps of the UMi model lowers delay spread after the RC’s inherent Q -induced smearing, thereby reducing the amount of absorber material needed to

meet specification limits (e.g., 55 ns that are otherwise costly to achieve in large chambers). Measurements across frequencies and absorber loads confirmed the efficacy of this “tap-removal” strategy. Second, a *keyhole-reduction* strategy for RC-based MIMO testing was proposed and validated in simulation: suppressing cross radio links in the emulator and introducing a LOS component (higher Rician K -factor) reduced keyhole effects and improved capacity without adding antennas—bringing the distribution closer to ideal Rayleigh behavior. This offers a practical pathway to higher-rank channel realizations in RCs with minimal hardware overhead, with physical validation and higher-order MIMO scaling set as future steps.

The report also emphasizes the analysis and comparison of multiple candidate link performance testing methods, focusing on design challenges, key performance impact factors, and real-world results comparison. Regarding the RTS method, a practical testbed based on the software-defined radio (SDR) platform was developed. Key functions and their impacts—such as antenna radiation pattern measurement using actual 5G NR downlink SSB reference signals, estimation and cancellation of the H-inverse matrix—were thoroughly investigated. Regarding the RC+CE approach, a novel two-step method based on RC PDP decoupling was proposed and extended from SISO to MIMO. Likewise, a practical implementation using a multi-channel SDR was developed and evaluated, with particular emphasis on FR2 MIMO link performance. Finally, an intercomparison of the two methods—RTS and RC+CE—based on real-world measurements demonstrated generally good agreement in link performance under selected scenarios.

Throughout the report, we kept a strong emphasis on *traceability and standards alignment*, with methods designed to dovetail with 3GPP/ETSI frameworks and validated, where relevant, via inter-laboratory comparisons to demonstrate reproducibility across sites. That emphasis underpins the metrological credibility required for regulatory acceptance and industrial uptake.

By unifying compact wireless-cable testing, generalized field emulation outside anechoic constraints, rigorous FR2 test-zone validation, dynamic sub-THz channel emulation, and RC-based delay/rank conditioning, this work advances a practical, standards-aware measurement science for 5G/6G radios. The resulting toolbox is both scientifically rigorous and industrially deployable—ready to be scaled, standardized, and transferred into conformance and performance test workflows.

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